

I-CISK
HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

Deliverable D5.3 -

Climate Data and Front and Back-End Components

I-CISK Climate Service Platform

Aug, 2025

Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge

This document is a revision of Deliverable D5.2 and presents an integrated and updated overview of the I-CISK climate service platform., which is developed within the I-CISK project.

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Author(s):	S.Bagli, P.Mazzoli, V.Luzzi, M.Renzi, F.Renzi, S.Pianini - GECCO B.Gräler, J.Schnell - 52N G. Bela - IDEAS Science Ltd. E. Romas -A.Ziogas EMVIS D.Castellana - RC510 A. Broekman, L. Pesquer, E. Prat - CREAM
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Executive Summary

This document, Deliverable D5.3, builds upon its predecessor and provides an integrated and updated overview of the I-CISK climate service platform. It covers both the climate data and the technical components that support it:

- **Back-end (Task 5.2):** This task details the behind-the-scenes infrastructure and data management.
- **Front-end (Task 5.3):** This task describes the user-facing interface and how users interact with the platform.

The core focus of this deliverable is how the platform is being implemented in the "Living Labs" (LLs) to address specific regional needs by combining scientific and local knowledge. This Deliverable D5.3 builds upon the previous versions of the platform's front-end and back-end components, initially developed in D5.1 and subsequently expanded in D5.2. In order to keep this deliverable consistent and accessible as a standalone document, it partially repeats - despite some editorial edits - what has previously been documented in D5.2 and has not received any technical updates. As an evolution of D5.2, this document maintains a similar structure and is organized into the following key sections:

Methodology

The I-CISK project follows a co-design approach where requirements are gathered, discussed, and verified collaboratively among stakeholders and between work packages. To streamline the process "Climate Service Task Forces" (CSTFs) have been established, which work together to define and refine climate services for each Living Lab, ensuring solutions meet local needs and are supported by robust data integration and processing frameworks.

General Platform Overview

The I-CISK platform is a cloud-based system utilising Docker and Kubernetes technologies for scalability and flexibility. It supports the ingestion, processing, and visualisation of climate data from multiple sources and derived information products, ensuring high performance and reliability. The architecture has evolved from initial designs, incorporating best-of-breed open-source components for enhanced functionality.

Common Components

Cloud Computing: Hosted on the Open Telekom Cloud (OTC), the platform leverages European data dissemination endpoints, fostering compliance and integration with European data infrastructures.

Climate Data Ingestor Docker: This component handles the ingestion of various climate data sources, transforming them into standardised formats for analysis. It supports FTP, CDS, and STAC Catalogues and is based on the python library [pygeoapi](#) providing OGC compliant APIs.

Living Labs Overview

Each Living Lab has tailored solutions for climate data integration, back-end processing, and front-end visualisation. This document details the specific components and methodologies used in I-CISK's seven Living Labs: Guadalquivir in Spain, Emilia Romagna in Italy, Rijnland in The Netherlands, Crete in Greece, Budapest in Hungary, Alazani in Georgia, and Lesotho.

Quality Goals and Testing

The I-CISK platform is designed with usability, accuracy, reliability, performance, and scalability in mind. Initial testing phases have focused on ensuring these quality goals are met through rigorous functionality, performance, and usability testing. User feedback has been instrumental in refining the platform, leading to improvements in navigation, data visualisation, and overall user experience.

Conclusion and Future Work

The I-CISK platform has successfully integrated diverse climate data sources and developed prototypes of robust tools for data analysis and visualisation. Remaining work will mainly focus on continuation of the services beyond the lifetime of the project, together with the hosts and stakeholders of the living labs.

This deliverable highlights the collaborative efforts in co-developing climate services that are not only scientifically robust but also tailored to local needs, ensuring their relevance and usability for stakeholders across different regions.

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1. Introduction

The I-CISK project, "Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge," aims to develop innovative climate services by integrating scientific and local knowledge to address the specific needs of various regions. This Deliverable D5.3 is a technical document, intended primarily for readers familiar with climate service technologies, data processing frameworks, and IT platforms. Thus, it employs technical language and specialised terminology appropriate for the target audience.

Deliverable D5.3 presents a detailed overview of the climate data, back-end (Task 5.2), and front-end (Task 5.3) components implemented within the project, with a specific emphasis on the Living Labs (LLs). The document builds on the components developed in earlier stages, particularly those described in D5.2.

The I-CISK project is built on a foundation of co-design, involving stakeholders from the early stage, so that the climate services developed are not only scientifically robust but also tailored to the specific needs of local user communities. The project employs a collaborative approach where requirements are gathered, discussed, and verified among stakeholders and work packages through the establishment of "Climate Service Task Forces" (CSTFs). These CSTFs are instrumental in defining and refining climate services for each Living Lab, ensuring that solutions meet local needs and are supported by robust data integration and processing frameworks.

The I-CISK platform described hereafter is a cloud-based system utilising advanced technologies such as Docker and Kubernetes for scalability and flexibility. It supports the ingestion, processing, and visualisation of climate data from multiple sources, seeking high performance and reliability. The platform's architecture has evolved to incorporate best-of-breed open-source components, enhancing its functionality and effectiveness.

Each Living Lab within the I-CISK project has developed tailored solutions for climate data integration, back-end processing, and front-end visualisation. These deliverable details the specific components and methodologies used in I-CISK's LLs in Spain, Emilia Romagna, Rijnland, Crete, Budapest, Georgia, and Lesotho developed by the end of the project.

After the initial testing phase, as detailed in the previous iteration of development, work has focused on ensuring quality goals through rigorous functionality, performance, and usability testing. User feedback received after the first round of implementation has been instrumental in refining the platform, leading to improvements in navigation, data visualisation, and overall user experience translated in the current versions.

In summary, Deliverable D5.3 highlights both the collaborative efforts in developing climate services that are scientifically robust and tailored to local needs, and the substantial progress in integrating diverse climate data sources, developing and pre - operational prototypes of robust tools for data analysis and visualisation, ready for scalability, integration with additional data sources, and support for more advanced climate models and algorithms.

2. Methodology

The CS platform has jointly been developed as an open-source solution. The source code is hosted at GitHub and will be made available within the GitHub organisation “icisk”: <https://github.com/icisk>.⁽¹⁾

Following the overall I-CISK project principle of co-design, the requirements of each Living Lab (LL) have been gathered, discussed and verified as a collaborative effort among several work packages (see D5.2.). The requirements have been collected as user stories (see Table 1). The user stories formulated by the LL leads and their stakeholders focus i.e. on the visualisation of local information products derived from large scale Climate Services, such as those developed by the Copernicus program. The analytical requirements to derive the essential information have only been implicitly contained in the user stories and needed to be further detailed by the corresponding domain experts in the I-CISK project.

In order to achieve an intense co-development of the actual solutions for each Living Lab based on the collected user stories, so called “Climate Service Task Forces” (CSTF) had been established in the I-CISK project. These CSTF define the day-to-day steering group for each LL and contain one representative of the LL and one from each WP. While this group is intentionally small, the representatives in each CSTF can of course build upon the team and work done in the WP they represent. Depending on the individual set-up and phase within the co-design process of each LL, the CSTFs met with different and varying intensities.

Each CSTF constitutes an agile development team where the LL representative acts as the “product owner” and takes responsibility that the CS under development suits the needs of the stakeholders of the LL. In an iterative process, first mock-ups (plain sketches or rudimentary functional components) have been presented and refined during discussions with LL leads, but also with stakeholders where appropriate. Discussions and decisions taken on the mock-ups informed the development of first prototypes for each LL, which have been presented and discussed first with the LL lead, as well with stakeholders. In this early stage of the prototype development, where different options are assessed and the vision of the CS, i.e. its user interface, still needs to converge within the CSTF, individual solutions building on related work of the involved partners had been developed. In order not to hinder these vibrant developments, the back-end components managing the data access have also been individually dealt with in each of the LL prototypes, often relying on only snapshots of data. In the recent phase of the co-development, the CSTF have decided upon the CS design and the prototypes have been harmonised, e.g. building upon the central CS data infrastructure of the I-CISK CS platform and also by re-using available front-end components among several LLs.

¹ Note: The present remainder of methodology has not changed since D5.2 and is repeated for improved readability.

Table 1 – Visualisation needs and user stories (updated)

LL	As a	[Role]	I'd like to have a visualisation where [Visualisation]	[purpose]
Georgia				
G01	As a	water manger	I can select a station and read the monthly mean streamflow for the next 6 months	in order to plan the dams energy production.
G02	As a	user	I can export specific widgets from bulletins/reports	so that I can share the information on my own website
G03	As a	user	I can receive bulletins/reports in Excel or Word document format (one for expert users and one easier to understand)	so that I can easily read the report, distribute a printed version or send it via email
G04	As a	CENN organisation	I can disseminate a map of the LL with different colours indicating the conditions of the streamflow forecasts	so that the local users can understand the information without much knowledge of the forecast details
G05	As a	farmer (small / medium sized farm)	I can learn about water availability in a very simple way (possibly a map)	to plan my irrigation
G06	As a	Manager at Melioration	I can obtain information on expected water availability for the coming season	To plan the water allocation to users, and whether restrictions are required in case of drought

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G07	As a	user from different sectors	I can compare the forecast for the monthly streamflow data (mean & percentiles) to historical reference data sets	in order to e.g. plan the dams energy production, irrigation ...
Spain				
ES01	As a	livestock farmer	I can view the historic time-series (for dedicated stations) temperature/precipitation data from drought of the 1990s alongside current temperature/precipitation downscaled forecast (SMHI+CREAF)	so that I can make informed decisions about my farming practices
ES02	As an	olive farmer	I can view drought (historic to projected) indicators (SMHI+CREAF), monthly mean temperature (min, max) and aggregated precipitation data in a map and per station	so that I can prepare for droughts in time
ES03		cooperate technician + farmer + agencies	I can access display information about the water table levels and the dynamics of groundwater in the region	so that I can better understand the water cycle in the area and its impact on agriculture and livestock practices
ES04		cooperate technician + farmer	I can know the production forecast of olives from LL based on the climate	so that I can know in advance the expected profit and resources needed for the harvest
ES05		cooperate technician	I can have direct access to the data and the ability to manipulate it myself, potentially through a Jupyter Notebook	so that I can perform my own analyses and gain deeper insight into the data

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ES06		cooperate technician + farmer	I can access crop productivity, agro climatic indicators (from Copernicus)	so that I can make informed decisions about my farming practices
Hungary				
HU01	As a	municipality official	I can access more scale relevant and detailed temperature heat maps	so that we can make informed decisions about developing green areas as an adaptation method to combat urban heat island effects
HU02	As a	resident	I can see information on adaptation methods within my home	so, I can better prepare for and cope with extreme heat events
Netherlands				
NL01	As a	farmer	of the potential precipitation deficit with one month lead time	to optimise my irrigation schedule/storage basin usage
NL02	As a	water authority	of the potential precipitation deficit with one month lead time with trigger values indicated	to inform stakeholders of upcoming drought measures
NL03	As a	recreational water tourist	of the likelihood of limitations in ship lock operations with up to one month lead time	to plan my tour/holiday accordingly
NL04	As a	tree nursery	of present and two weeks outlook of the salinity of the surface water at my farm	such that I can plan my water storage/management
NL05	As a	farmer	where I can access if drought is going to occur more frequently/severe in the next 5 – 25 years	such that I can decide on my investments (storage, irrigation type, seeds, fertiliser, ...)

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Greece				
GR01	As a	water manager	of the available surface water for the next wet period of the year (November to February) up to more than 6 months in advance with regular updates	to decide how the permits for water usage will be distributed among municipalities/farmers
GR02	As a	water manager	where I can compare the forecasts for the available surface water for the current season to historical data	to decide how the permits for water usage will be distributed among municipalities/farmers
GR03	As a	hotel owner	of the TCI (tourism climate indicator) for the main touristic period (April – October) with monthly updates 6 months in advance	to decide upon touristic activities that will be offered by the hotels & decide on which time periods to focus with promoting their tourism products
GR04	As a	port manager	of the prevailing winds for a certain period of the year as a climate projection for the next 10 years (to be specified further)	to decide on works planning regarding port management and protection measures
Italy				
ITA01	As a	Technician Env, Agency	Of forecast of river discharge daily up to 1 month as time series graphs compared with historical data, uncertainty by boxplot with statistical distribution of forecast	to evaluate the integration of our products with new forecasts and improve the accuracy of our water resource management decisions.
ITA02	As a	Technician of the land Reclamation Authority	Of comprehensive data on river discharge and hydrometric levels, including short-term and long-term forecasts, and access projections on seasonal water availability and variability. This as maps and	Better anticipate emergency measures, optimize water distribution adjustments, and prioritize distribution among different sources.

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			graphs (internet page (with tools), uncertainty through statistic fork, or range of variability and comparison between the expected data and the real one	Develop proactive irrigation plans and reduce reliance on costly or less sustainable water sources
ITA03	As a	Technician of the Regional Government involved in Water Protection and Management Planning	Of short-term river discharge forecasts at key points in advance, in form of graphs and tables, errors eventually statistic forks if feasible	<p>Enhance the decision-making capabilities of water resource managers and adopt updated rules for environmental flow management while preserving ecological values.</p> <p>Anticipate alert related to approaching thresholds.</p> <p>Reduce instances of regulatory non-compliance and administrative interventions.</p> <p>Enhance operational decision-making and avoid unnecessary escalation to drought emergency protocols.</p>
ITA04	As a	Technician of a water utility company	<p>Access periodic data from single hydrometric stations and other critical points, including forecast and historical data, Lead time up to 1 month.</p> <p>Receive early warning notifications for significant flow changes</p>	<p>Enhance our emergency response measures and ensure uninterrupted water supply to our customers.</p> <p>Mitigate risks of water supply interruptions and alert in advance for possible reactivation</p>

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ITA05	As a	Hydropower plant operator	Of a single station up to 3-6 weeks discharge forecast graphs or tables, statistics forks otherwise error metrics, output at predefined catchments or sub catchments, presented in both graphical and tabular formats	Schedule maintenance during low flow periods, minimize the impact on energy production, and ensure optimal operational efficiency
Lesotho				
LS01	As a	Anticipatory Action coordinator at the Lesotho Red Cross Society	of the seasonal precipitation forecast probability (below average) for each district in Lesotho	when I prepare the early actions before the start of the raining season
LS02	As a	Hydrologist at the Department of Water Affairs	of the water storage level, relative to the dead storage, for each water reservoir in Lesotho	when I prepare a monthly report on the status of the water reservoirs in country

3. General Platform Overview

3.1. Technical specifications of the I-CISK platform – summary and update from D5.2

The developments are grounded in the architecture design that has been developed from the start of the I-CISK project and that was initially outlined in Deliverable D5.1 and further detailed in D5.2. Throughout the close cooperation with the Living Labs within the co-design of the separate Climate Services, the architecture of the I-CISK Climate Service Platform has been continuously refined to the actual final release. ⁽²⁾

One major adaptation in contrast to the initial architecture design proposed in D5.1, is the renunciation of GeoNode³ as a central web framework of the I-CISK CS platform (compare Sec. 6.1 and 6.2 in D5.1). A suitability assessment showed that the complete GeoNode set-up is not flexible enough to incorporate all the management, processing and visualisation needs that have been identified for the I-CISK CS platform. Therefore, the Web framework has been based on the best-of-bread open-source components in a modular way. This also includes some of the components of the GeoNode framework, such as the GeoServer. As outlined in the updated Figure 1 (compare with Figure 8 in D5.1), the GeoServer has a central role for the data provision within the CS platform. However, it did not remain the only internal data provider and was supplemented e.g. by provision of raster and time series data stored as ZARR-files or JSON. The data ingestor component handles the import and transformation of the different data sources. This component builds upon the open-source solution pygeoapi⁴, that already provides several OGC APIs for easy re-use of data and processes in subsequent modelling steps and clients.

Figure 1– Final whitebox architecture diagram of the web framework based upon Figure 8 from D5.1.

² Note: The architecture has not changed since D5.2 and is repeated for ease of readability.

³ GeoNode Website: <https://geonode.org/>

⁴ pygeoapi Website: <https://pygeoapi.io/>

3.2. Common Components

Cloud Computing - Telecom Cloud

Note: The Cloud Computing provider has not changed since D5.2 and this section is repeated for improved readability.

The CS platform is deployed and operated in the Open Telekom Cloud⁵ (OTC). The OTC is also a contributor to the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, becoming the “*main dissemination endpoint for the Copernicus data*”⁶. This, and being a European provider led to the selection of the OTC as a computing environment.

The services for the living labs including the landing page are organised in one specific namespace in our kubernetes cluster at the OTC. The namespace uses common infrastructure components shared with all namespaces like the cert-manager with a cluster issuer and a nginx ingress controller. The cert-manager uses “Let’s Encrypt” infrastructure to request and maintain the required certificates for the ingresses of the namespace.

Each “component” in the namespace has its own workload, service, ingress and optional persistent volume claims for providing storage. A component in this context is either a living lab’s app or the landing page. The set-up of the apps differs depending on the implementation. The Rijnland app for example, uses two deployments, one for the front and one for the backend. The orchestration of all components is done using kustomization.yaml. Hence, each living lab app comes packaged in a container image and kubernetes is used to specify the environment and resources. More details about each application can be found in the following sections.

Climate Data Ingestor Docker -

The Climate Ingestor Docker is a crucial component of the I-CISK project’s cloud-based Climate Service (CS) platform. Its primary function is to handle the ingestion of various types of climate data from multiple sources, ensuring that the data is accurately fetched, processed, and stored for further analysis and visualisation.

⁵ Website of the open Telekom Cloud: <https://www.open-telekom-cloud.com/>

⁶ announcement of cloudferro: <https://cloudferro.com/news/copernicus-data-space-ecosystem-becomes-the-main-copernicus-data-dissemination-endpoint/> [accessed: 13th June 2024]

Figure 2 – Climate Data Ingestor infrastructure (https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKIAEdbo=?share_link_id=151574016194)

The Climate Data Ingestor infrastructure is based on Pygeoapi, making the component consistent and OGC compliant and ingests data described in Table 2

Table 2 - Available datasets that are used in the Living Labs through the ingestor at <https://i-cisk.dev.52north.org/data/collections>

Title	Description	Type	Datasets	API/Link	Living Lab
AEMET_stations	Temperature and precipitation data	Collection Feature	AEMET	<Link to AEMET data>	Spain
cems-glofas-forecast	River discharge data for a set of stations with a lead time of one month	Collection Feature	CDS	https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/cems-glofas-forecast	Italy
cems-glofas-seasonal	River discharge data for a set of stations with a lead time of six months	Collection Feature	CDS	https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/cems-glofas-seasonal	Georgia
creaf_forecast	Temperature and precipitation data	Collection EDR	CREAF	OTC bucket	Spain
georgia_alazani_shaqriani_hydro	Historical river discharge for Alazani-Shaqriani station	Collection Feature	Daily updated CSV file	FTP Service ftp:mepa.gov.ge	Georgia
georgia_historical_discharge	Historical river discharge for a set of stations	Collection Feature	Static GeoJson file	OTC bucket	Georgia
SMHI Seasonal Forecast	SMHI river discharge data	Collection Feature	SMHI	FTP Service ftp://ftp.smhi.se	Georgia, Italy, Lesotho
SPI Forecast	Forecasted SPI index	Collection EDR / Feature	CDS	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/seasonal-original-single-	Georgia

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				levels	
SPI Historical	Historical SPI index	Collection EDR / Feature	CDS	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/seasonal-original-single-levels	Georgia
italy_historical_COUT	River discharge historic data for EmiliaRomagna Stations	Collection Feature	ARPAE	Web page: https://simc.arpae.it/dext3r/	Italy
knmi_evapo_obs	Potential precipitation deficit from KNMI	Collection Feature	KNMI	<Link to KNMI data>	Netherlands
knmi_evapo_obs_forecast	Forecasted potential precipitation deficit from KNMI	Collection EDR / Feature	KNMI	<Link to KNMI data>	Netherlands
lesotho_drought_forecast	Lesotho drought forecast	Collection EDR	CDS	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/seasonal-monthly-single-levels	Lesotho
ll_spain					Spain
seasonal-original-single-levels	Forecasted precipitation and temperature	Collection EDR	CDS	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/seasonal-monthly-single-levels	Georgia, Lesotho
Bias corrected temperature and	Bias corrected data for forecast temperature	NetCDF file	CDS	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/s	Spain

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precipitation	and precipitation			easonal-original-single-levels	
sis-agroclimatic-indicators					Spain
emilia-romagna_arpae-stations_river-discharge	River discharge for EmiliaRomagna Stations	Collection Feature	ARPAE	https://dati-simc.arpae.it/opendata/osservati/meteo/realtime/realtime.jsonl	Italy

For each data source, one or more ingestor processes are defined as Pygeoapi processes. These processes can be executed manually via a REST API call or automatically through scheduled invocations, configured by editing a scheduler file that specifies the dataset, query, and frequency. The scheduler is composed of cron jobs hosted on Kubernetes within the OTC.

Upon completion, each ingestor process creates a ZARR file storage in a cloud bucket for raster data, or a GeoJSON file for vector data, and updates the Pygeoapi configuration with a new collection referencing the file path. For improved performance and data persistence, ZARR files can also be stored directly within the Pygeoapi instance if a volume is configured. Once a new collection is generated, its data can be directly queried via OGC API.

The ingestor processes support data from FTP and CDS sources. A detailed description of the Climate Ingestor Docker's components and functionalities is provided below.

Components of the Climate Ingestor Docker:

1. Scheduler

Function: The Scheduler component is responsible for triggering the fetching of new data at regular intervals. It ensures that the platform is updated with the latest available data from various sources.

Features:

- Can be configured to fetch data at different frequencies (e.g., hourly, daily, weekly).
- Supports multiple schedules to accommodate different data sources and their update frequencies.

2. Data Fetcher

Function: The Data Fetcher component connects to external data sources and retrieves the required data. It handles different data formats and ensures seamless data transfer.

Features:

- Supports continuous data ingestion from various sources such as Copernicus, ECMWF, SMHI, and local weather stations.
- Manages connections and data fetching protocols (e.g., API requests, FTP downloads).

3. Data Processor

Function: The Data Processor component is responsible for transforming raw data into a standardised format that can be stored and analysed by the platform. It performs necessary data cleaning, conversion, and aggregation.

Features:

- Converts data into cloud-optimised formats (ZARR), particularly for raster data.
- Ensures compatibility with the platform's data storage and retrieval systems.
- Handles different data types, including time-series, spatial (raster and vector), and textual data.

4. Individual ingestors for Data Sources and Living Labs (LLs)

Function: These components are specialised ingestors tailored to specific data sources and Living Labs. Each ingestor is configured to handle the unique requirements and data formats of its designated source or LL.

Features:

- Customised setup for continuous data ingestion from specific sources.
- Dedicated ingestors for setting up and managing individual data for each LL, ensuring tailored data processing and storage.

Functional Workflow:

- Initialization: The Scheduler triggers the Data Fetcher based on the configured schedule.
- Data Fetching: The Data Fetcher connects to the external data source and retrieves the new data.
- Data Processing: The retrieved data is passed to the Data Processor, which cleans, converts, and standardises the data.
- Data Storage: The processed data is stored in the database according to the defined schema.
- Continuous Update: The cycle repeats at the next scheduled interval, ensuring the platform is continuously updated with fresh data.

Technical Specifications

- Dockerization: Each component is containerized using Docker, ensuring isolated, scalable, and maintainable deployment.
- Cloud Integration: Optimised for cloud environments, enabling flexible and scalable resource management.
- Modularity: Designed with a modular architecture, allowing easy updates and integration of new data sources and processing algorithms.

The Climate Ingestor Docker plays a pivotal role in the overall functionality of the CS platform by ensuring timely, accurate, and efficient ingestion and processing of climate data. This enables stakeholders to access up-to-date and relevant climate indicators, aiding in informed decision-making and climate adaptation strategies.

General Climate Data Downscaling Process

The Data Analysis Tool (comp. Fig. 9 of D5.1) will be extended by a particularly designed process, which allows the application of downscaling and bias correcting forecasted data based on historical time series data. This Service is available through an OGC API Processes instance provided through pygeoapi and will be seamlessly integrated with the Data Analysis Tool along with other processing components. Hence, it can be integrated into custom workflows. This process is supposed to be widely applicable (across Europe and for different variables) and will therefore not be compatible with the highly optimised downscaled and bias corrected data provided by SMHI, but it will allow a wider application of the CS platform supporting its re-use and longevity.

Common Landing Page Web Docker

The landing page⁷ uses a common web server landing page container image based on the nginx:latest image with a few additional files for styling and templating. These include bootstrap css, font and javascript files.

The page itself is injected as a plain html page using a kubernetes configmap. The entries of the configmap are mounted as files in the landing page container. This allows us to extend and adjust the landing page without the need to rebuild the complete image. The linked CS can be run internally in the same infrastructure or reference external services hosted at I-CISK partners.

The initial version of the landing page has been reworked to mimic the design of the I-CISK project website. It consists of different tiles for each living lab and two extra tiles to link to the project's website and GitHub organisation (see Figure 3).

52°North | I-CISK Living Labs Server

Project Resources

Figure 3 - The updated version of the landing page with different tiles for each living lab, plus two extra tiles to link to the project's website and GitHub organisation mimicking the I-CISK's project website.

⁷Currently available at: <https://i-cisk.dev.52north.org/>

4. Climate Data and Back-End Components (Task 5.2) and Front-End Components (Task 5.3)

The I-CISK project aims to create advanced climate services that blend scientific and local knowledge to address the specific needs of various regions. The primary goal is to develop and implement tools for integrating, processing, and visualising climate data to provide accurate and actionable information for stakeholders across multiple Living Labs.

For the back-end, the development involves building a cloud-based infrastructure using tools like Docker and Kubernetes to ensure scalability and flexibility. The Climate Data Ingestor Docker component handles the ingestion of various climate data sources, transforming them into standardised formats for analysis. This system supports multiple data sources, for compliance with OGC standards (using Pygeoapi). Advanced algorithms are used to process raw data, including bias adjustment and downscaling, to generate actionable climate indicators and forecasts. Data is stored in cloud-optimised formats in a centralised repository, for easy access and efficient management.

The front-end development focuses on creating user-friendly interfaces that allow stakeholders to access, visualise, and interpret climate data easily. These interfaces, built with frameworks like Shiny (R), React (JavaScript), and Leaflet, provide various tools for data visualisation, such as time series plots, heatmaps, and statistical charts. Users can customise their views and interact with maps and graphs to explore relevant data. The front-end applications are also designed to be responsive, ensuring compatibility with mobile devices.

By integrating these back-end and front-end components, the I-CISK project aims to deliver comprehensive climate services that are scientifically robust and highly usable, supporting effective decision-making for climate adaptation and risk management in diverse regional contexts. Additionally, the back-end components have been developed to support potential upscaling and out scaling efforts, enabling the transfer of services to other geographic areas or application contexts.

Each of the following subchapters is devoted to a specific Living Lab and will provide detailed information on the development process, structured into the following main points:

- **Climate Data Integration and Back-End Components:** This section covers the methodologies and technologies used to integrate and process climate data, including data sources, processing algorithms, and storage solutions.
- **Front-End and Web GUI:** This section describes the design and functionalities of the user interfaces, detailing how users can access and visualise the climate data through interactive tools and features.
- **Summary and outlook:** This section provides a brief *non-technical* summary of the technical section above and outlines future developments and enhancements planned for the climate services in each Living Lab, based on ongoing feedback and evolving stakeholder needs.

The technical details for each Living Lab differ significantly as they reflect the unique development specifics of each climate service.

4.1. Andalucía Living Lab (Spain, LL1)

Climate Data Integration and Back-end components

This LL features five different CS organised as tabs in a single web application. A key data sources for LL1 are downscaled Geo-TIFFs with high spatial resolution of 250m/pixel edge created by WP3 (CREAF) that include historical data (since the year 2000) of precipitation, mean temperature and a set of drought indices as well as 6 months forecasts of precipitation and mean temperature.

The seasonal forecast workflow is composed of two main steps: bias correction + downscaling:

- 1) On the ECMWF-Seas5 seasonal prediction models (51 members), two bias adjustment methods - Distribution Based Scaling (DBS) and Multi-scale bias AdjuStment (MidAS) (Berg et al., 2022⁸) - are applied for each percentile of the empirical quantile mapping cumulative distribution function from the daily data time series. A table of bias-correction factors is obtained in the reference period for each meteorological station of the AEMET dense network by accounting for differences between model estimated values and reference observations. These factors apply to coming seasonal forecasts for each point location of all meteorological stations.
- 2) Geostatistical downscaling is composed by multilinear regression (MLR) with residual interpolation (Ninyerola et al., 2007⁹). The variables used in the MLR are elevation, aspect, potential radiation (calculated for each month and year), and distance to the coastline. The residual interpolation method is Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW), using a fitted exponent parameter. Using the center pixel of each raster cell (250 m spatial resolution), we generate continuous maps for each of the 51 ensemble members of the seasonal forecasts for monthly temperature and precipitation. In the climate service, selected quartiles from these 51 predicted models are presented...

Furthermore, LL1 also integrates agroclimatic indicators¹⁰ for the period from the year 2011 until 2040 accessed from the Copernicus' Climate Data Store (CDS), namely:

- consecutive summer days
- consecutive dry days
- summer days

An additional resource are the station data sets from AMET are integrated for the extensive time spans available. The stations provide precipitation and temperature data, and the corresponding CS allows for different comparisons, such as per time period or variables.

Apart from these climate datasets, the Climate Service includes detailed data and information about the local aquifer and its hydrogeological dynamics, and additional geo data representing municipalities and areas of interest.

The modelling process developed by CREAM is integrated into the CS back-end and allows to directly generate Cloud Optimised Geo-TIFFs (COG) stored in the OTC Object Datastore. From there it can be directly used in any front-end application.

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-6165-2022> .

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-006-0264-2>

¹⁰ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/sis-agroclimatic-indicators?tab=form>

To integrate the data provided by CDS, it is downloaded to a persistent volume in the cloud and loaded from there. Since this data is using a climate projection until 2099 it is not continuously updated and is technically treated as static data.

All additional geo data is maintained manually through the integration of a geopackage (.gpkg) file obtained from the LL. The OTC supports versioning of files which is used in this case to keep track of any changes of this data set.

To aggregate and transform tif-files, workflows have been developed based on `gdal_merge` and `gdal_translate` which both are provided by the GDAL¹¹ binaries.

In addition, Github actions are utilised as deployment pipelines.

Implementation of bias correction procedure

Purpose: This process is developed to monitor seasonal forecasts of minimum/maximum temperature and precipitation over a six-month horizon, with the goal of providing bias-corrected values at specific station locations. Forecast data are often affected by systematic errors due to model limitations; therefore, bias correction techniques are applied to align forecast statistics with historical observations, ensuring that the output is interpretable and consistent with the climatological context. In this case, the focus is not on a gridded field but on delivering corrected values for irregularly distributed station points. This enables direct use in operational monitoring, local climate assessment, and early-warning systems where station-level accuracy is critical.

Methodology: The process is fully automated and runs at the beginning of each month to coincide with the availability of the seasonal forecast at monthly intervals, retrieving seasonal forecasts initialized in the current month and covering the following six lead months. Source data comes from a regular grid and are interpolated onto an irregular station-based grid using bilinear interpolation. The bias correction is based on quantile mapping (Q-Q relation). Correction factors are pre-computed and stored, for every combination of:

- Station
- Initialization month [1 ; 12]
- Lead month [1 ; 6]
- And for each of the 51 ensemble members from the Copernicus seasonal forecast system.

For each station and ensemble member, forecast values are matched to their corresponding quantile using the forecast climatology, and then mapped to the corresponding observed quantile from historical data. This approach ensures that the statistical distribution of corrected forecasts reflects the observed variability at each location.

Dataset: The input data source is the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) SEAS5 Seasonal forecast daily and sub daily data on single levels, which provides ensemble-based seasonal forecasts at global scale.

Output: For each of the three variables — daily minimum temperature, daily maximum temperature, and daily precipitation — the final bias-corrected dataset is stored in NetCDF format and uploaded to an S3-compatible object storage. Each file contains corrected forecasts for all 51 ensemble members, structured by station, variable, and time step, making the data ready for direct ingestion in downstream systems or climate services.

¹¹ GDAL is a translator library for raster and vector geospatial data formats <https://gdal.org/index.html>

Front-End and Web GUI

For improved performance and longevity, the CS has been redeveloped in React and features the OpenLayers and OpenPioneer frameworks. The GUI consists of several tabs, one for each climate service provided. The tabs separate the application by different functionalities e.g. one for investigating the observations of the past 25 years, but also Climate projections up to 2040. The CS features different functionalities for comparison and therewith assessment of variables but also time spans. Additionally, an introduction about I-CISK and the particular LL is provided.

Figure 4 – Start of LL1 application showing different functionalities separated by tabs at the top.

Users can select different datasets (e.g. temperature, precipitation or drought indices) and select time spans to be shown or compared with each other. When clicking into the map the time series that is displayed will be based on the nearest pixel clicked. Within the map, users can navigate freely using standard map interactions such as panning and zooming. To help users navigate, and since their use case is highly location specific, features are included to zoom either to the full extent or predefined areas of interest.

Pronósticos meteorológicos mensuales a medio plazo (hasta 6 meses)
 Este servicio ofrece pronósticos estacionales de precipitación y temperatura para los próximos seis meses. Los mapas muestran el percentil 50 de 51 miembros del pronóstico, con corrección de sesgo a nivel estacional seguida de una regresión lineal múltiple con interpolación de residuos, con una resolución espacial de 231m. Al seleccionar un píxel, se visualiza gráficamente la serie temporal con los percentiles 5 a 95, facilitando el análisis de incertidumbre.

[Cazorla](#)
[Los Pedroches](#)
[General](#)

2000

Julio

Seleccione la variable:

Temperatura *i*
 Precipitación *i*
 Índices de sequía *i*

Índice de sequía (SPEI) 9 meses

descargar datos

descargar datos

Figure 5 – Example of two climate services.top: detailed forecast for 6 months; bottom: interpolated observed data, here: comparison of SPEI 9 months for July in 2000 and 2024.

React is a standard web development framework providing a rich functionality of user interactions, design and visualisation elements. Additionally, the OpenPioneer Framework is used, easing the development of state-of-art Web Map Applications featuring the OpenLayers as map framework. According to the user stories, comparison of variables and time periods are a crucial means to better understand past and future climate and weather conditions. Therefore, selection elements based on radio buttons, checkboxes, drop-down menus and sliders are used throughout the different CS of LL1. The map display is intentionally kept simple, and controls are grouped outside of the map display. Only the legend is plotted inside the map window. In order to underpin the continuous nature of the continuous data, the legend now shows a colour gradient with a few ticks in contrast to discrete colours. Furthermore, map legend colours have received the same styling in terms of background and transparency, to ensure that the colours can be precisely mapped to each other. An additional slider under the map allows to “swipe” between two individually selected layers in order to ease the visual comparison between two layers, as e.g. from two different years. On clicking into the map, time series plots of the selected variables at the particular location are displayed under the map allowing to inspect the temporal development at particular locations, e.g. a farmers field. Examples of interactive maps and data plots are provided in Figure 5 above including map plots and charts of the variables of interest.

No programming skills are needed for the users of the Climate Services. The front-end application is aimed towards end users. Interactions are done by clicking. In addition, all texts are provided by the LL to guarantee native (Spanish) speakers understand all elements. Furthermore, information boxes are included to add context to elements, such as data origin, and describe their functionality as shown below in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Example of information box describing the methodology behind the data, here for the drought indices SPI and SPEI.

Summary and outlook

The Climate Services of the Living Lab in Spain focuses on integrating and visualising climate data to support local stakeholders. The main data sources include high-resolution downscaled Geo-TIFFs created by CREAM, which encompass historical data and six-month forecasts. Additionally, agroclimatic indicators from

Copernicus' Climate Data Store (CDS) are used to provide detailed climate insights, as well as extensive weather observations and hydrological data.

Data integration involves downloading remote data, downscaling, aggregating and interpolating it into Cloud Optimised Geo-TIFFs, and storing it in the Open Telekom Cloud for easy access. The CDS data, projected until 2099, is treated as static and stored in a cloud-based persistent volume. Additional geographic data, such as municipal boundaries are manually integrated and versioned to ensure accuracy.

The front-end application developed using React, OpenPioneer and OpenLayers, offers an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI) with multiple tabs for different climate services. Users can interact with the data by selecting datasets, comparing time spans, and navigating maps with ease. The application is designed to be user-friendly, requiring no programming skills, and is fully localised for Spanish speakers. Features like zooming and predefined areas of interest help users focus on relevant data.

The Living Lab's user stories are well defined and mostly covered with the preoperational CS in place. The CS have been presented to and evaluated with LL hosts and stakeholders for continuous improvements.

4.2. Emilia Romagna Living Lab (Italy, LL2)

Climate Data Integration and Back-end components

The main data sources for LL2 are forecast daily discharges at one or more "stations" corresponding to specific river sections. Such knowledge could be generated from seasonal projections produced by project partners (e.g. SMHI) in WP3.

Alternatively, discharge forecasts generated by upstream services Copernicus' Climate Data Store/CEMS Early Warning Data Store (such as and monthly and daily river discharge forecast from GLOFAS/EFAS systems¹²) are exploited as well. Forecasts shall be compared with local observational data (particularly river discharge @ local hydrometric gauging station nearby named "Lugo", see Figure 7. The climate data integration process includes the implementation of improved (e.g. bias-adjusted) discharge forecasts provided by WP3 from SMHI; post-processing algorithms are applied to generate actionable climate indicators and forecasts. Detailed methodologies for these processes are outlined in WP3.

As described, local data (river daily discharge that corresponds to the water level recorded at the called "Lugo" gauging station, Figure 7, managed by Regional Environmental Agency ARPAE and publicly available together with downstream station of "Ponte Veggia") are collected to feed the process and to be available in the service for obtaining relevant statistics. Local Information from ARPAE can be retrieved automatically from online repositories (like river stage recordings) then converted by the service into discharge via local stage-discharge relation at the gauging station, made available by the same Regional Agency (at the time of writing "Lugo" is the only station with such information available) ; ingestion phase of such data is described hereafter.

¹² <https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/cems-glofas-seasonal?tab=overview>

Figure 7 - The Lugo hydrometric station used in the climate service.

The architecture of the Emilia Romagna climate service platform is built on a cloud-based infrastructure, utilising Docker containers. Key components include the frontend-service, backend-service, data ingestor, data storage.

The frontend-service is a node-js based docker, which combines React, OpenLayers, Highcharts libraries to visualise maps and charts.

The backend-service is based on pygeoapi and serves data like timeseries to the frontend. Climate models and algorithms are also executed from the backend-service as customised processes.

The data ingestor handles the retrieval and preprocessing of climate data, which are then stored in a S3-like data storage and/or a Database. This component effectively supports the Integration between external climate services and the new climate service. The ingest process retrieve data from ARPAE real-time dataset (<https://dati-simc.arpae.it/opendata/osservati/meteo/realtime/realtime.jsonl>), which t is a Json file containing data for a set of stations and variables in Emilia Romagna region. This dataset is filtered to obtain only river level values for the stations of Lugo and the downstream sections of Ponte Veggia. Once filtered, the data is saved as a GeoJson file and the previous invocation is updated with the new data, so that the data accessible via Pygeoapi collection is always updated with fresh data.

The platform, as anticipated, integrates data from external climate services like Copernicus and SHMI, alongside local datasets provided by regional stakeholders such as ARPAE.

Custom IT components for LL2 include specialised data processing pipelines and interfaces designed to handle the specific requirements of the regional stakeholders. These components provide seamless integration and

efficient processing of both global and local climate data, supporting the delivery of tailored climate service. For example, the service allows to customize and elaborate local uploaded data (e.g. assigning a stage-discharge curve). The main components are reported hereafter:

Docker: The platform uses Docker containers to ensure a consistent and isolated environment for running different components of the system.

PyGeoapi: is a Python server implementation of the OGC API suite of standards. The project emerged as part of the next generation OGC API efforts in 2018 and provides the capability for organisations to deploy a RESTful OGC API endpoint using OpenAPI, GeoJSON, and HTML. pygeoapi is open source and released under an MIT licence.

Kubernetes: Manages container orchestration, ensuring the system can scale efficiently and handle varying loads.

S3-like storage: S3 is an object storage service that stores data as objects within buckets. An object is a file and any metadata that describes the file. A bucket is a container for objects. Files from the data-ingestor are initially saved in the s3-system.

Database Systems: Stores historical and real-time data in a structured format, enabling quick retrieval and analysis.

The main functionalities are described in the following sections:

Real-Time Data Integration:

The system integrates real-time observational hydrometry data published for selected stations in the catchment. This data is used to provide up-to-date information on river stage converted into discharge for the stations where the stage-discharge relation is known. Near real time stage recordings are available in the ARPAE online drive, which is openly accessible (¹³).

Forecasting:

The service provides future predictions of river flow based on ensemble weather forecasts as provided by hydrological models. Forecasts are available as dynamic selectable daily projections or as predefined multiple time horizons, (such as monthly periods, Figure 9)

Statistical Analysis:

The backend allows statistical calculations of various relevant percentiles (e.g., 50%, 25%-75%, 5%-95%) and other statistical measures (such as extremely low flow conditions, fraction of the ecological flow of the river), which are crucial for understanding the trend and the natural variability in the river flow data and trigger activation-deactivation of withdrawals.

Uncertainty Analysis:

Assesses the uncertainty in the forecasts by analysing the spread of ensemble model outputs (e.g. 10-90th percentile in Figure 10). This helps in understanding the confidence level of the predictions.

By performing these statistical calculations in the backend, the system provides actionable and comprehensive forecasts, along with a clear understanding of the variability and uncertainty inherent in the data. This supports effective decision-making and planning for water resource management in the Emilia Romagna region.

¹³ <https://dati.arpae.it/dataset/dati-dalle-stazioni-meteo-locali-della-rete-idrometeorologica-regionale>

Front-End and Web GUI

The platform is designed with accessibility in mind, offering a graphical user interface that does not require programming skills to operate. Tooltips, guided workflows, and comprehensive help documentation are provided to assist users in navigating and utilising the platform effectively [2].

The Web-GUI has been developed exploiting the following main components:

- Living-lab-react-template created simplifying the r berry-free-react-admin-template
- React-map is an interface component to visualise raster-files and shapefiles. This is an OpenLayers map wrapped into a react-component driven by a simple QGIS project.
- Ensemble-chart is a react chart component for forecasts visualisation. Written in javascript it allows the visualisation of forecasts series and historical data and related ensembles just by switching view.

The first version of the GUI (online demo) was produced early in 2024, after preliminary discussions on visualisation examples and requirements, shared among stakeholders during online and physical meetings. After a few months of testing, one-to-one interviews have been arranged to obtain detailed feedback on this demo with focus on graphical aspects, usability, preferred visualisations, bugs and suggestions for improvement of the GUI to feed the next round of development.

A second version of the GUI is now online, following examples (Figure 8 to Figure 10) show how the interface looks like in the current release.

The web GUI is designed to be user-friendly and accessible, featuring a dashboard that allows users to select variables, stations, and lead times of interest. The interface supports interactive visualisation of data through graphs, tables, and maps, ensuring that users can easily interpret and utilise the information provided.

Climate data is made accessible by interactive charts that display daily forecasts together with recorded values and relevant statistics; the actual landing page of the service is reported in the following figures.

Figure 8 – GUI landing page with station list (left), station position on the map (center) and dashboard to activate specific graphs with access to station data and the forecasts available (right).

Details of the key visualisations accessible through the main page are available in next figures.

Forecast Date of Lugo #101

GLOFAS ▾

BoxPlot ▾

Figure 9- average forecast volumes in the coming season, provided versus historical average in the same period obtained from the last 10 years of observation, includes statistical variability, in boxplot fashion.

Forecast Date of Lugo #101

GLOFAS ▾

Ensemble ▾

Figure 10 – Forecast discharges selectable through the GUI; custom forecast window on a daily basis has been chosen among available, with capability to activate-deactivate statistical forecast percentiles to improve legibility and understand forecast variability.

Detailed comments on the actual interface are provided hereafter:

User Interface Components

1. Header Section:
 - Title: “Living Lab2 Italy” – indicates the specific Living Lab and region for which the climate services are being provided.
2. Left Sidebar:
 - Navigation Menu:
 - All Stations: A link to view all available weather and climate stations within the Living Lab region.
 - Lugo/PonteVeggia: Specific link to the climate data and forecasts for the station of interest
 - ICISK Home Page: A link to the main page of the I-CISK project for broader project information and resources.
 - Version Information: Displays the current version of the platform (e.g v1.0.45), which indicates the developmental stage of the interface.
3. Main Map Display:
 - Interactive Map: A detailed map showing key geographical locations such as main cities and surrounding areas. This map provides spatial context for the climate data and allows users to pinpoint specific locations and stations of interest.
 - Markers: Indicates the location of gauging level/discharge stations (e.g., “Lugo” or “Ponte Veggia”) where data is being collected and monitored.
4. Right Panel – Data Visualization:
 - Forecast Data (for the selected station):
 - Date Slider: Allows users to select the forecast date range, including past periods for inspection and *a posteriori* evaluation of performance of previous forecasts.
 - Graphical Display: A time-series plot depicting streamflow forecasts in cubic metres per second (m^3/s). The plot includes various percentiles (e.g., 50th, 10-90th, 20-80th, etc.) to show forecast uncertainty and variability.
 - Legend:
 - Forecast Percentiles: Different shaded areas represent forecast percentiles to indicate the range of possible outcomes.
 - Streamflow Observations: Historical data of streamflow to compare with forecasts.
 - Thresholds: Markers such as “Above Normal,” “Below Normal,” and “Extreme Low” provide reference points for interpreting the forecast data Vs relevant thresholds like the Ecological flow and the fraction of ecological flow that is met.
 - Ensemble Dropdown: Allows users to select different ensemble models or forecasting scenarios to view how various model outputs compare.
5. Additional Features:
 - Zoom Controls: Options to zoom into specific pre-defined time frames (like 1 month) for a more detailed view.

Interpretation

- Observed Streamflow: The slider shows the actual measured streamflow values up to roughly the previous month (supposed to be the end of recordings), providing a baseline for comparison.
- Forecasted Streamflow: The forecast box plots indicate expected streamflow for the upcoming period, with percentiles showing the range and uncertainty of these predictions.
- Comparison: Users can compare observed data with forecasted data to understand expected changes and variability in river flow, which is crucial for water resource management and planning. Similar options are provided in Box plot view where Users can compare cumulative observed data

in past similar periods with forecasted data in the coming period, to better evaluate expected forecasted values versus real past conditions.

Interaction and User Flow

- **Selecting Stations:** Users can select different gauging stations from the left sidebar to view specific data and forecasts for those locations. This option is also provided on the background map. Obviously this function is relevant from the perspective of extending a similar service towards more complex monitoring networks than the two station example in this case.
- **Navigating Time Frames:** The date slider and zoom controls on the right panel allow users to adjust the forecast period and explore different temporal resolutions of the data together with historic data.
- **Analysing Data:** The interactive daily and average plots enable users to visually analyse spatial and temporal patterns in forecasted/observed data, activating/deactivating information on uncertainty, inspecting single values, thus aiding informed decision-making processes for water resource management applications.

Forecast Date Slider and Data Visualisation

At the top of the interface, a date slider allows users to adjust the forecast date range displayed. In the current setup, this slider covers a period that includes both recent observed data and forecast data, enabling users to contextualise upcoming scenarios against historical conditions from the previous months.

The main graphical representation is provided through daily forecast and box plots (see Figure 8 to Figure 10) which display the distribution of both observed and forecasted streamflow values. Each graph is titled to indicate the forecast period shown, with the vertical axis representing streamflow in cubic meters per second (m^3/s) and the horizontal axis divided into time periods, distinguishing the recent past observations from the upcoming forecast periods.

Observed data for the past period are overlaid to current daily forecast for daily values or represented in blue in box plots for cumulated values (Figure 9), illustrating the range of measured streamflow values and highlighting key statistics such as the 50th percentile (median), interquartile range (25%-75%), and the broader variability range (5%-95%). Similarly, forecast data are presented in red box plots for cumulated values (Figure 9), or ensemble ranges (Figure 10) for daily ones using the same percentile structure. This consistent visual language allows users to directly compare historical patterns with predicted future flows, clarifying variability and uncertainty in a user-friendly format.

The legend adjacent to the graphs explains the colour coding and percentile ranges, clearly distinguishing between observed and forecasted data. Additionally, a dropdown menu to choose the representation of interest is located at the top right of the graph area, enabling users to select alternative visualisation types or customise data representation to better fit their analysis and decision-making needs.

This GUI provides a comprehensive and user-friendly interface for accessing and analysing forecasts, supporting the objectives of the I-CISK project to deliver tailored climate services.

Application

- **Decision-Making:** This visualisation aids stakeholders in making informed decisions regarding water allocation, storage and release, and drought preparedness (e.g. emergency protocol activation and information to final water users)
- **Analysis:** The statistical ranges help users assess the reliability and variability of forecasts, enabling more robust planning and adaptation strategies.

The actual release of the visualisation tool within the LL2 Climate Service platform provides a comprehensive and intuitive way to monitor and forecast river flow, setting the ground for a pre- operational climate service that supports effective water resource management in many similar hydraulic nodes across the Emilia Romagna region.

No programming skills are needed to use it. The front-end application is aimed towards end users with basic knowledge of hydraulic and hydrology. Interactions are done by simple operations like clicking and dragging cursors in addition, self-explaining legends are provided.

Summary and outlook

The Emilia Romagna Climate Service Living Lab focuses on integrating and visualising climate data to support regional water resource management. It primarily uses daily discharge data at specific river sections, supplemented by open forecasts from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CEMS-GLOFAS) or proprietary SHMI E-HYPE model. Data is collected, stored, and pre-processed, including bias adjustment when available, to foster accuracy and usability.

The platform is built on a cloud-based infrastructure using Docker containers and includes frontend and backend services, data ingestors, and storage. The frontend, developed with Node.js, React, OpenLayers, and Highcharts, allows users to interact with maps and charts without needing programming skills. The backend, based on pygeoapi, processes and serves data to the frontend.

The system integrates external climate services data with local datasets from stakeholders like the Regional Environmental Agency ARPAE, seeking for high-resolution, localised climate information. Users can visualise real-time data, forecasts, and statistical analyses, aiding in effective decision-making for water management, checking forecast versus ecological flow related thresholds that trigger activation-deactivation of the withdrawals.

Further possible enhancements towards a scalable operational service include further customizations to the interface, e.g. to accommodate more gauging stations or updates to the stage-discharge curve, averaging and summarizing the statistical forecast over different time periods (e.g. weekly) to derive synthetic performance indexes (like Threat Score or rate of hit, miss and false alarms in forecasting ecological flow thresholds, as recently described in D3.4 about user driven evaluation of climate services).

4.3. Rijnland Living Lab (Netherlands, LL3)

Climate Data Integration and Back-end components

The main data source for LL3 are river discharge predictions provided by WP3 (SMHI). Accompanied by open data at selected gauges provided by Rijkswaterstaat (Dutch Water Management Authority) providing local real time observed (as well as historical) data. Additionally, data from the Copernicus Climate Data Store is integrated for a precipitation deficit map. The local data is also included in the downscaling and bias correction performed by SMHI (see D3.1 for details). The data is provided for download through SMHI's ftp server, obtained on a regular basis and stored on the OTC. Further local data is integrated through local websites with specific information for the different user groups.

Meanwhile, the entire retrieved, downscaled and processed data is stored in the central internal storage component and linked to the data catalogue of the I-CISK platform. The open data from Rijkswaterstaat is accessed through an API provided by Rijkswaterstaat and integrated into the CS.

The current back-end component of this CS is a docker container that mainly runs Python code. It performs the download of the monthly updated NetCDF-file holding the downscaled and bias corrected data from SMHI and stores it in the OTC. A flask API¹⁴ for the front-end that requests data is then provided as a json response for easy plotting. Github actions are used to trigger the deployment pipeline whenever a new feature is added, such that the publicly deployed version of the CS always provides the latest development state for review through the LL hosts or their stakeholders. The CS has up to 4 different CS, depending on the user group that has been selected.

¹⁴ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/stable/>

Recreatievaart Landbouw **Waterbeheer** Boomteelt

Recreatievaart Landbouw **Waterbeheer** Boomteelt

Droogtebeeld

Afvoer Lobith

Neerslagtekort

Klimaat

Week 29 | 14.07 - 20.07

Week 30 | 21.07 - 27.07

Week 31 | 28.07 - 03.08

Week 32 | 04.08 - 10.08

Week 33 - 36 | 11.08 - 07.09

Week 37 - 40 | 08.09 - 05.10

Week 41 - 44 | 06.10 - 02.11

← Menu

Rijnafvoer te Lobith

Klimaat

Laag Water ⓘ

Individuele voorspellingen **Bandbreedte** Gemeten afvoer

Figure 11: Screenshots of the Rijnland CS

A brief description of the Front-end GUI component is provided below:

- top-left:** Menu of 4 CS for the user group “watermanagement”;
- top-right:** calendar week view with a colour precipitation deficit summary, here: all dark red.
- middle:** up to 6 months forecasted runoff of the Rhine at Lobith, a central indicator for the water management.
- bottom:** Derived precipitation deficit map as of 15th July 2025 of The Netherlands zoomed to Rijnland.

The design of the CS has been extensively discussed through initial mock-ups with the LL hosts and their stakeholders. Based on the selected user group, a selection of CS is presented, all openly accessible for transparency among the user groups. No programming skills are needed to use the CS, as they clearly focus on end users. Interactions are done by “clicking”. The developed CS features different interactive elements. Figure 11 gives a static overview of all components. Figure 11 (top-left) displays the menu for the user group water management where the CS in Figure 11 (top-right) is designed for all user groups providing a very concise and colour coded overview of the precipitation deficit by calendar week.

Figure 11 (middle) depicts the time series plot showing gauge levels at the gauge Lobith along with user controls to change the current view of the plot. Users can choose between a view of observed and forecast data or only forecast data. They can also switch between a view of all 51 single ensemble members or the

statistics of the ensemble members displaying the 10th, 30th, 50th, 70th and 90th percentile. When the user hovers over the single runs, individual time series are highlighted, and precise forecast values are shown in a small pop-up window. In case the percentile view is selected, the small pop-up window contains the mean and the ranges of the 10%-90%- as well as the 30%-70%-percentile bands.

Figure 11 (bottom) shows a map-based CS, which depicts the observed and forecasted precipitation deficit based on ensemble data from the Copernicus Climate Data Store. The data is regularly updated and the indicator derived in the CS platform. Different locations can be selected from the map, to inspect the temporal development of this particular point. This CS also informs the calendar week overview, which is calculated as the maximum per week over the entire Rijnland region.

Another CS summarises the projected climatic development of the region and is accessible from different locations in the web application to guide the interested user. The climatic projection is treated as static data and visualisations, as it is not regularly updated.

The CS is developed in React and features the OpenLayers and OpenPioneer frameworks, all free and open-source front-end JavaScript based libraries.

Summary and outlook

The Rijnland Climate Service Living Lab integrates discharge predictions from SMHI and historical water level data from Rijkswaterstaat. Using bias-adjustment and downscaling algorithms, the platform provides accurate climate data for local water management. Furthermore, a precipitation deficit is derived from Copernicus data and visualised as a map-based CS and informing a concise calendar week summary for the region.

The backend processes and stores data using APIs and custom components, as a fully integrated system. The frontend, built with React, displays interactive graphs of historical and predicted data, allowing users to easily interpret forecast data without programming skills. Additional links lead to further external information specific to the user group.

4.4. Crete Island Living Lab (Greece, LL4)

Climate Data Integration and Back-end components

Climate is a critical factor for the tourism sector, influencing decisions on when and where to travel, and posing challenges for tourism-dependent economies. The Living Lab of Crete provides a series of climate indicators related to tourism and tourism activities which are grouped in the following categories:

Essential Climatic Variables. Seasonal forecasts of climatic variables such as air temperature, precipitation, humidity are obtained from ECMWF through Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S).

Hydrological Variables and indicators. This category includes river outflows at catchment-level which are provided through seasonal hydrological forecasting.

Climatic Tourism Indicators. Climatic indicators are easy-to-understand metrics that provide specialised and tailored made information to activities related to tourism. The climatic indicators are derived from essential climatic variables and are produced with a forecasting horizon of 7 months.

Infrastructure Indicators. This category contains indicators related to critical infrastructure that may affect tourism activities.

Data sources, acquisition and preprocessing

During the ICISK project, EMVIS developed seasonal climate services tailored to the needs of its end users in the Living Lab of Crete. While the development of a central operational IT platform to support service deployment across all Living Labs, was included in the ICISK DoW, EMVIS chose to deliver its services through its own **proprietary web-based platform**.

This decision was made based on strategic, technical, and operational considerations. EMVIS has developed mature, production-ready systems that are already in use by its clients in other operational domains, such as flood forecasting, water quality forecasting, coastal monitoring etc. By leveraging this existing infrastructure, EMVIS was able to further develop a platform and deploy, demonstrate, and deliver its climate services to end users significantly earlier than would have been possible through the central ICISK platform. As a result, EMVIS engaged the end users of the Cretan Living Lab quite early into the co-evaluation approach, achieving multiple iterations of hands-on demonstrations, feedback and service customization. This approach ensured higher user engagement and trust. In addition, the use of EMVIS proprietary platform aligned with its broader business strategy to maintain and evolve a unified service environment across multiple domains. Furthermore, the EMVIS's development team had the opportunity to gain new insights by following up closely the development of the Open Telecom Cloud platform, increased experience and new knowledge uptake and further exploit I-CISK's specific exploitable asset (web platform). This approach reinforced EMVIS's brand identity and strengthened its sustainability and commercialization plan even beyond the scope of the ICISK project. The pre-operational CS developed for Crete LL has been connected and is available through the Open Telecom Cloud platform.

Climate indicators

Climate indicators for the LL of Crete are calculated by combining diverse data and information through 3 different sources:

Copernicus Climate Data store

Seasonal forecasts for meteorological variables such as air temperature and precipitation, humidity, wind speed etc. are downloaded operationally from Copernicus Climate Store (CDS) for the entire Island of Crete, using the seasonal-original-single-levels product provided by ECMWF. This product is obtained in netcdf format through CDS Application Program Interface (API) using an api-key that allows programmatic access to seasonal forecasts. The downloaded netcdf files are further pre-processed in order to: a) down-sample the native spatial resolution ($1^{\circ}\times 1^{\circ}$) resolution down to 250×250 m²; b) calculate ensemble statistics by manipulating the individual simulation members; and c) convert accumulated precipitation values to daily precipitation totals. The temporal frequency of the forecasts is preserved, i.e. 6-hours timestep for temperature and 24-hours timestep for precipitation. The LL uses seasonal forecasted variables from two distinct models, i.e.:

- Set III - Atmospheric model Ensemble 15-day forecast (ENS)
- Set IV - Ocean Wave Model Ensemble 15-day forecast (ENS-WAM)

The pre-processed netcdf files are stored in EMVIS's cloud-based servers.

Seasonal Hydrological forecasting workflow provided by SMHI.

Seasonal probabilistic hydrological forecasts are obtained operationally through SMHI's FTP server for the 42 hydrological catchments of Crete. HYPE's model output files in txt format are downloaded directly from this server.

Each forecast contains daily values of Flowrate, Evapotranspiration and Corrected Precipitation for a forecasting horizon of 214 days. The 51 individual members of the ensemble hydrological forecasting are merged into a single file per hydrological variable and are stored to EMVIS's cloud-based server.

Local datasets and information

Some indicators incorporate information from local datasets for the island of Crete, such as geological maps, digital elevation models, roads networks etc. These static datasets are stored in various formats (e.g., shapefiles, geotiffs, netcdfs) and are retrieved by the operational post processing scripts.

Processing scripts

EMVIS calculates in total 16 variables for the Living Lab of Crete as described below, which are updated monthly with scripts written in Python.

Essential Climate Variables

Temperature, Precipitation and other meteorological variables are aggregated into netcdf files using a 15-days reference period and the produced files are uploaded to geoserver so they can be visualised in the front-end.

Hydrological Variables

Catchment Outflow. The 51 hydrological members obtained by SMHI, are used to calculate statistical properties of the ensemble such as average, minimum and maximum values of catchment outflows, as well as percentiles (25th, 50th and 75th) which are used to quantify the uncertainty of forecasted variables. The daily forecasted hydrological quantities are processed to calculate weekly averaged values of catchment outflows and are then converted to time series which are uploaded through APIs to the central database of EMVIS platform, so they can be visualised in the front-end.

Another hydrological indicator calculated for Crete is the Wet Period Flow Volume which is defined as the total discharge of a catchment during the upcoming wet period (November to February). This indicator is of special interest for the one end-user (Organization for the Development of Crete- OAK), which needs this information early in spring of every year in order to plan efficiently the allocation of water resources between tourism, agriculture and other critical water demanding sectors. Taking into consideration that hydrological forecasts are available for 7 months ahead, different strategies are used to estimate each catchment's potential during the wet period (see also Figure 12. During March and April, when seasonal forecasts do not provide information for the upcoming wet period, climatology data provided through SMHI for the historical period of 1980-2020, are used as the only source of information to estimate the wet period flow rate. During May to July, seasonal forecasts which cover only partially the wet period, are combined with climatology, while from August to November seasonal forecasting is used exclusively. Finally, during December to February seasonal hindcasts and forecasts are used to estimate the potentially available water quantity.

Figure 12 - Methodology for calculation of water availability during the upcoming wet period.

Climatic tourism indicators

Tourism Climatic Index. The Tourism Climatic Index (TCI) evaluates the climate favourability for outdoor tourism by combining climatic variables related to the human comfort levels. The variables used in the calculation are 1) maximum daily temperature; 2) minimum daily humidity; 3) mean daily temperature; 4) mean daily humidity; 5) mean monthly precipitation; 6) mean monthly daily sunshine duration; and 6) monthly mean wind speed. TCI is calculated on a 0 to 100 scale. Values close to 0 represent unfavourable conditions, while values close to 100 represent ideal conditions.

Precipitation Frequency is an indicator used to describe how favourable are the climate conditions for tourism activities. It is calculated by the number of days that the daily accumulated precipitation is higher than specific thresholds, and it is expressed as a percentage over the reference period (15 days). Frequency of precipitation is calculated with different thresholds, i.e. 1, 10 and 50 mm that correspond to Light, High and Extreme precipitation respectively.

Extreme Hot Days & Tropical Nights is another family of indicators based on outside air temperature, which describe the attractiveness of tourism destinations. Frequency of Extreme Hot Days is calculated by the number of days that the Maximum daily temperature exceeds 35 oC, and it is expressed as a percentage over the reference period (15 days). Frequency of Tropical Nights is calculated by the number of days that the Minimum daily temperature does not drop below 20 oC, and it is expressed as a percentage over the reference period (15 days).

Cooling Degree Days (CDD) are a measure of how much (in degrees), and for how long (in days), outside air temperature was higher than a specific base temperature and is directly related to the energy demand for cooling residential buildings. CDD is calculated using a base temperature of 25 oC, and assuming that no cooling is needed when the outside temperature is below this threshold. CDD are calculated for a period of 15 days and are presented as the daily average for that period.

Infrastructure indicators

The Instability Index is used to quantify the susceptibility and hazard of landslides and slope failures in a specific area. The index is calculated taking into consideration multiple factors (e.g., distance from roads, slope inclination, slope orientation, lithology, hydrogeological conditions, rainfall conditions, land use, distance from streams, distance from tectonic elements, elevation) and is calculated on a 0 to 100 scale with higher values indicating a higher risk of landslides.

All hydrological variables are aggregated using a 7-day reference period while variables of the other three categories are aggregated using a 15-day reference period.

Marine Navigation

This category includes indicators related to marine navigation which affect port operations. Strong North (N) and Northwest (NW) winds exert significant forces on the breakwater and seawalls of the most important Cretan ports that are located in the North part of the island. Strong South and (S) winds overload floating docks and piers and affect the safe mooring of ships and vessels. In addition, this category also monitors oceanographic parameters such as the significant height of combined wind and sea swell, wave direction and period.

OAK dashboard

In addition to the indicators, EMVIS has developed an interactive dashboard to support OAK in its water allocation planning. The dashboard provides a clear overview of essential hydrological information, including the expected water volume for the upcoming wet period for each one of the 5 reservoirs managed by OAK. It also enables users to compare seasonal forecasts for each catchment against historical records, helping classify the forthcoming hydrological year as dry, wet, or average. This decision-support tool enhances OAK's ability to allocate water resources efficiently and plan proactively for competing demands.

Automation

All seasonal indicators are updated on a monthly basis with a forecasting horizon of 7 months. Essential climatic variables, Climatic Tourism Indicators and Infrastructure indicators are updated on the 6th of each month, while Hydrological variables are updated on the 10th. This is due to the update frequency of the datasets used. The update is performed using automated Python scripts scheduled using Cron functionality and Celery server for asynchronous task scheduling.

Bias adjustment

Information provided by the SMHI-HYPE hydrological model is downscaled and bias corrected using local datasets of precipitation measurements provided for the island of Crete. This is described in more detail in work package WP3.

Backend Components

The information generated for the Living Lab of Crete is provided through a web-based interactive platform that allows users to visualise the forecasted indicators. The platform is built mostly with open-source IT tools and programming stacks, and all components have been selected carefully to ensure the robustness, flexibility, and extensibility of the final solution. The DJANGO web framework serves as the back-end core of the web-based ICISK platform. PostgreSQL database with PostGIS extension will be used to store all types of numeric and geo-spatial information that needs to be managed by the platform, while GeoServer implements the web mapping service that provides high quality maps of environmental information to the end users through their web-browsers.

At the same time the platform facilitates data exchange and communication of the different technological components and workflows that need to be coupled for operationalizing the complete service line of ICISK. A rich set of API services have been created to allow the individual workflows (e.g., scripts used for the production of hydrological and climate indicators) to communicate with each other as well as to serve the generated data into the Graphical User Interface.

The platform is deployed in cloud computing services (as explained at the beginning of the chapter) using 3 individual machines for the Backend, the Geoserver and the Frontend. Figure 13 presents the technology stack that has been used for the implementation of ICISK platform.

Figure 13 – Technology stack of the CS co-designed for the Living Lab of Crete.

Front-End and Web GUI

The frontend is the Presentation Layer of the platform which receives the stored information from the database and the GeoServer and renders it as maps and graphs in an interactive web-based Graphical User Interface (GUI). The GUI acts as a single endpoint for visualising, accessing and interacting with the information generated for the Living Lab of Crete. The interactive web elements and user controls of the GUI are developed on React JavaScript, while Leaflet is used for the interactive mapping environment of ICISK platform. Chart.js is used for the implementation of the interactive charting functionality used for presenting time series of forecasted parameters.

The platform is available at [I-CISK Services Landing page](#), and contains two separate tabs for the Hydrological Variables and the Tourism Related Indicators.

The hydrological information is visualised in a map which presents the delineation of the 42 hydrological catchments of Crete. By clicking on any catchment on the map or by selecting a catchment id from the dropdown box, the user is able to visualise the timeseries of the seasonal forecasted variables as a chart element (Figure 14). The graph also contains a boxplot element (Figure 15) that presents the spread of the probabilistic hydrological ensemble, through statistical properties (e.g., average, median, percentiles).

Figure 14 – Seasonal forecasts of catchment outflow for the hydrological catchments of Crete.

Figure 15 – Statistical properties of the seasonal hydrological forecasts for a selected catchment.

The Climate Tourism indicators are presented in a separate tab as spatial heat maps which visualise the variability of the selected indicator across the area of interest, for the selected time period. A time bar component at the bottom of the screen allows the users to navigate to all available time-steps of the forecasting horizon which automatically update the map (Figure 16). By clicking on a point in the map the user is also able to visualise the forecasted variable as a time series in the chart element (Figure 17).

Figure 16 – Map presenting the Instability Index calculated for Crete.

Figure 17 – Seasonal forecast of Cooling Degree Days indicator for Chania city, in Crete.

The interactive map supports several basemap layers such as satellite, topographical and street, which provide geographic context and allow the easier interpretation of the map, including basemaps. Additionally, a collection of thematic layers can also be enabled in the map, presenting information related to sub-basins, rivers and lakes, roads, airports, cities etc.

The interactive dashboard developed for OAK is presented in a dedicated tab and includes three customized graphs designed to support informed decision-making for water allocation:

- 1) **Wet Period Inflows:** An overview graph displaying the total volume of water expected to flow into the 5 reservoirs managed by OAK during the upcoming period (November to February), based on the latest hydrological forecasts.
- 2) **Forecast vs Historical Comparison:** A comparative graph showing forecast discharges for the next seven months against historical simulations (1980–2020), enabling users to assess the current forecasts in relation to historical percentiles.
- 3) **Forecast Evolution:** A time series graph illustrating how the predicted wet period inflows evolve as the wet period approaches and hydrological forecasts are progressively updated.

Figure 18 – Interactive dashboard for OAK’s water allocation planning, in the Living Lab of Crete.

Summary and outlook

The Crete Climate Service Living Lab provides climate indicators crucial for tourism, including temperature, precipitation, and hydrological forecasts. Data is sourced from the Copernicus Climate Data Store, SMHI, and local datasets, then processed using bias adjustment and downscaling.

The backend uses Django, PostgreSQL with PostGIS, and GeoServer, with Python scripts automating monthly updates. The frontend, built with React, Leaflet, and Chart.js, offers an interactive web GUI for visualising maps and time series.

The actual platform allows users to view hydrological forecasts and climate indicators through an easy-to-use interface.

4.5. Budapest Living Lab (Hungary, LL5)

The Budapest Living Lab focuses on addressing urban heat-related challenges, particularly the Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon, using advanced thermal imaging combined with artificial intelligence methods. The following sections explain how climate data are collected, integrated, and processed through back-end technological components.

Climate Data Integration and Back-end components

Heat mapping in the 8-12 μm radiation range, combined with artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, is a powerful tool for urban planning and climate action. This approach offers several significant benefits for understanding and addressing urban heat islands (UHIs) and other thermal-related urban challenges in the Budapest LL.

The core of the back-end component is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) component providing a machine learning algorithm that predicts the surface emission temperatures in densely populated areas of big cities during hot summer days. To have a reliable dataset for the training phase of a machine learning algorithm, heat measurements were carried out during a hot summer day of two districts of Budapest. The results of these measurements are 2 large GeoTIFF files stitched from many ortho images and thermal images respectively. The two files are stored on the server and post-processed for faster access through the client. The GeoTIFF format has additional geographical metadata besides the pixels, which helps to match ortho and thermal imagery data from the exact same location during further processing.

The following subsections detail the specific technical processes used to transform large-scale ortho and thermal imagery into actionable thermal maps for the Budapest Living Lab. The described methodologies include preparing the datasets required to train the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), configuring the CNN architecture, and handling the critical task of accurately converting colours into thermal values. Finally, an overview of planned future improvements is provided, emphasizing openness and community involvement in further developing these innovative climate service tools.

Preparation of training and test data for CNN training

The training and test data set consists of 2 sets of tiles which are generated from the large GeoTIFF files coming from ortho and thermal measurements of the same geographical location. The tiling is useful for processing large images in manageable pieces, especially when training CNN, as it reduces the computational load and can help to more efficiently manage memory usage. Each ortho tile has a corresponding thermal tile used to train the model.

These tiles are loaded into memory using PyTorch Dataset built-in functionality modified by inheritance. The ortho and thermal data are loaded into a custom Dataset object when the `'__init__'` method is called.

CNN architecture

The used convolutional neural network has 3 layers illustrated below:

Figure 19 – Layers of the Convolutional Neural Network as used in the LL to produce thermal imagery from ortho imagery.

Dependencies: Python 3.11, PyTorch 2.2, Numpy 1.24, Pillow 10.2

The result of CNN training is a trained machine learning algorithm which can predict heat images from ortho data.

Colour scale handling.

The results of the thermal measurements are encoded into a GeoTIFF file where the measured values are represented by colour values. In order to use them, a proper conversion is needed which is based on a

colour scale which is encoded into a separate GeoTIFF file. The related implementation is in HeatScale class. The 'load_colors_from_image' method reads the pre-prepared image file which must contain only the colour scale. The found colours and the mapped thermal values are loaded into a dictionary object, which provides an efficient way to find a corresponding thermal value by a colour. The mapping is linear which means that every step in the colour scale has the same associated heat step in the entire scale.

Matching heat and colours in heat files

The colour-heat mapping does not contain all the possible colour values which can be found in the heat tiles. Therefore, when the heat tiles are loaded into memory an approximation method is needed to find a closest heat value represented by the processed colours. The approximation works by finding the colour value which has the smallest difference vector in the RGB vector space. Then the associated heat value is used for the colour in question. The approximation is implemented in the 'findClosestOne' method.

Future work

The back-end CNN model used for predicting thermal images is under continuous development for improved accuracy, and to provide more reliable predictions. Additionally, the CNN model and raw data will be published as open source, allowing users to generate heat maps for any urban environment if they have remote ortho-photos or satellite images, fostering greater community engagement and collaboration.

Front-End and Web GUI

The front-end and graphical user interface of the Budapest Climate Service Living Lab, accessible online via the public platform city.zcan.eu, provides stakeholders—including urban planners, researchers, policymakers, and citizens—with an intuitive and structured entry point to urban climate information. The platform's content is methodically organized into clearly defined main sections (Home, CityZcanHub, APPs, CityZcanView, Maps, Game, and Bilingual Support), each designed with a specific user-oriented purpose in mind. Users can easily navigate the site, engaging with interactive mapping tools, downloading open datasets, accessing sensor documentation, and utilizing interactive applications tailored to enhance their understanding of urban heat phenomena and climate adaptation strategies. Below, each main section is briefly introduced, clearly outlining its function and key contents to guide the reader's exploration of the platform.

[city.zcan.eu – Full Website Description](#)

Overview

city.zcan.eu is the public-facing platform of the Budapest Climate Service Living Lab. The platform provides a range of features and resources, including interactive maps, research documentation, open datasets and device specifications for CityZcanHub. It also offers educational resources in both English and Hungarian.

Main Sections

The website is organized into several main menu sections, each serving a specific purpose. A detailed description of each is provided below.

Figure 20 – homepage of the platform.

The homepage offers a comprehensive introduction to the project, clearly articulating its purpose and scope.

The mission of the Budapest Climate Service Living Lab is to support climate adaptation in Budapest through advanced sensing, open data, and accessible tools.

This platform is designed to address the pressing need to accurately measure and predict urban heat in densely populated districts, with the ultimate aim of informing effective planning decisions and enhancing citizen awareness about environmental issues.

Provides a concise overview of the site's primary offerings, encompassing interactive maps, available downloads, research background information, details regarding CityZcanHub, prototypes of applications, and educational games.

The website offers straightforward navigation.

Figure 21 – board handling the sensors.

This menu is dedicated to introducing CityZcanHub, a modular sensor system for monitoring urban environments.

It also contains a brief overview of the interior, explaining the function of each sensor and how they work together. Relevant posts about usage and events are included here, too. Required documents (datasheets, user guide) are uploaded here as well.

APPs

The purpose of the APPs menu is to bring together all available data, scripts and maps in one place, encouraging open science and collaboration by making raw and processed data freely available.

Provides open access to orthophoto and thermal imagery tiles collected for the two study districts Terézváros and Erzsébetváros.

Open-source scripts are also accessible through this menu for both:

CityZcanView

Thermal image viewer plugin for the FIJI environment, calibrated for the Lepton 3.5 chip found in CityZcanHub.

Heat map analysis script.

This is a Python script that automatically groups urban surfaces by colour and material. It combines thermal and visual orthophotos to calculate temperature statistics and displays the results in easy-to-understand graphs.

Maps

Figure 22 –example of generated map.

The Maps section represents the interactive core of the platform.

- Visual Exploration: Users can explore high-resolution orthophotos, thermal images, and CNN-predicted thermal maps of Terézváros and Erzsébetváros.
- Contextual Reference: An OpenStreetMap (OSM) layer is provided for easy contextual reference.
- Intuitive Navigation: The interface offers user-friendly controls for zooming, panning, and switching between different map layers.
- Comparative Analysis: The platform enables a side-by-side comparison of measured and predicted thermal distributions.

The objective of this page is three-fold: firstly, to provide planners with an accessible visual tool with which to comprehend temperature variations; secondly, to offer researchers a means of identifying urban heat hotspots; and thirdly, to empower citizens to engage with this issue.

Game

An educational board game ("Thermoform Your City") was also developed as part of the broader public-engagement strategy, aimed at raising awareness about urban heat islands and climate adaptation planning. This component is extensively described in Deliverable D2.7 and is therefore only briefly mentioned here for completeness.

Bilingual Support

city.zcan.eu is fully bilingual, with all content accessible in English and Hungarian.

- Users can easily switch languages via the site's top menu.

- Ensures local accessibility for Budapest residents and stakeholders while supporting international research collaboration.
- Reinforces the platform’s commitment to inclusivity and wide engagement.

StreetMap /Ortho Photo/Heat Image Layers Display

Choose a district: Choose a map layer:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037293.

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StreetMap /Ortho Photo/Heat Image Layers Display

Choose a district: Choose a map layer:

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Figure 23 - Examples of map layers for one of the two districts in Budapest under study. The upper map shows the observed thermal image, while the lower map depicts the output of the CNN based on an ortho image.

Summary and Outlook

The Budapest Climate Service Living Lab represents a comprehensive and forward-looking approach to tackling the challenges of urban heat islands (UHIs) through advanced data collection, machine learning, and public engagement. By combining high-resolution orthophotos and thermal imagery in the 8–12 μm range, the project builds a robust foundation for data-driven urban planning. The core of the back-end component—the convolutional neural network (CNN)—demonstrates the power of artificial intelligence to predict surface temperatures across complex urban landscapes, offering a scalable solution for monitoring and mitigating heat in densely built environments.

The integration of these capabilities into a publicly accessible platform (city.zcan.eu) underscores the project's commitment to open data, transparency, and collaboration. The website serves not only as a repository for research outputs, maps, and datasets but also as an educational hub designed to engage planners, researchers, and citizens alike. Features such as the interactive map viewer and the educational board game "Thermoform Your City" highlight the project's emphasis on making climate science both understandable and actionable.

4.6. Alazani River basin Living Lab (Georgia, LL6)

The updated version of the Georgia Climate Service is an interactive web platform developed as part of the I-CISK project, supporting climate risk-informed decision-making in the Alazani River Basin. It provides localized, user-friendly access to climate and hydrological forecasts, SPI drought indicators, and climate projections tailored for local communities, farmers, water managers, and policymakers.

Climate Data Integration and Back-end components

The Georgia Living Lab utilises a comprehensive approach to integrate diverse climate data sources to support accurate climate forecasting and risk assessment for the Alazani and Iori River Basins.

The primary data sources include:

- Seasonal Forecast of River Discharges [Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute \(SMHI\)](#)
- [Copernicus Seasonal forecast daily and subdaily data on single levels](#)
- Copernicus System GLOFAS
- [Copernicus ERA5-Land hourly data from 1950 to present](#)

The SMHI and GLOFAS river discharge datasets are used to provide seasonal forecasts for river runoff, while ERA5 and Copernicus re-analysis data are used for drought-related indicators.

A crucial aspect of developing effective climate services involves bias correction, which leverages local data and knowledge. For the Georgian Living Lab, we utilized bias-corrected weather forcing data from SMHI to generate river discharge forecasts and applied tailored bias correction factors for monthly accumulated temperature and precipitation forecasts.

The following subsections present detailed descriptions of the advanced methodologies and computational workflows implemented in the back end. The latter subchapters are, in more detailed fashion, devoted to illustrating how back-end components dedicated to Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) monitoring and bias correction of seasonal forecasts have been systematically implemented.

Data Handling:

For the Georgian Living Lab, the acquisition of climate and hydrological data involves multiple sources and workflows. Seasonal river discharge forecasts provided by SMHI and local daily water discharge measurements (available only for the Shakriani River) are routinely ingested via automated FTP transfer. Additionally, global datasets such as GLOFAS and ERA5 are obtained through the Copernicus Climate Data Store API. Following ingestion, all datasets are systematically stored in a centralized, cloud-based S3-compatible storage, optimized specifically for high-volume and frequently updated climate data. This infrastructure ensures robust data integrity, quality control, and streamlined access for downstream processing and analysis.

Implementation of Bias-Adjustment, Downscaling, and Post-Processing Algorithms

The integration phase merges these acquired datasets with local observations and relevant complementary information to create a coherent and comprehensive climate dataset tailored specifically to the Alazani River Basin. A critical step in this integration process is the implementation of advanced data-processing

algorithms—including bias adjustment, spatial downscaling, and hydrological post-processing—fully described in detail within WP3 deliverables of the I-CISK project.

These algorithms refine the raw forecast data, improving accuracy and spatial relevance to meet stakeholder needs. For example, forecasts provided by SMHI undergo an automated hydrological rescaling procedure to adjust river flow rates specifically for any chosen Point of Interest (POI). This method, known as the "drained area hydro method," rescales forecasted discharge values based on the specific drainage area of each local sub-basin. By computing the drainage area for each POI relative to the reference basin originally used in SMHI forecasts, the procedure produces localized forecasts that more accurately reflect the hydrological realities of the Alazani catchment.

Ensemble Forecasting: Statistical Analysis and Visualization

Function: Ensemble Statistics and Percentile Computation

The forecast service also includes a comprehensive statistical analysis module that processes outputs from an ensemble of 50 hydrological forecast models provided by SMHI. This component systematically calculates key statistical metrics—such as mean, median, standard deviation, variance, and specific percentiles (5th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 95th)—to effectively quantify forecast uncertainty and variability. The resulting data are structured in an accessible format, optimized for visual interpretation via interactive front-end tools. This enables stakeholders to rapidly grasp forecast uncertainties and better plan their adaptive actions.

Automatically Compute Skill Assessment Comparing Hindcast with Real Data

To continuously assess the reliability and accuracy of forecasted outputs, the Georgia climate service includes a robust automated skill assessment module. This module routinely compares historical forecasts (hindcasts) against observed discharge measurements from past events, allowing the evaluation of model performance across several critical skill metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Correlation Coefficient, and systematic Bias. The results, clearly presented in detailed performance reports, provide critical insights into model strengths and help to identify priority areas for improvement and model recalibration.

Standard Precipitation Index (SPI) monitoring:

Purpose: The Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) is a widely used indicator to monitor drought conditions based on precipitation anomalies. It quantifies the deviation of precipitation from the long-term climatological average, normalized to allow for comparison across different regions and time scales. The SPI-3 specifically reflects short- to medium-term precipitation deficits over a 3-month period, making it suitable for assessing seasonal drought impacts on water resources, agriculture, and ecosystems. (*EDO & GDO, 2025, [Factsheet SPI](#)*)

Methodology: The SPI-3 index is computed using a standardized methodology consistent with international guidelines, particularly those from the European and Global Drought Observatories and the WMO. The core of the method is a statistical transformation of precipitation data into standardized values that describe deviations from the climatological norm.

The entire process is fully automated and executed at monthly intervals via a scheduled cron job that activates a PyGeoAPI-based service. This service is configured to:

- Retrieve and preprocess the necessary precipitation data from the preceding month,
- Perform all computational steps to derive SPI-3 values at the grid and basin levels.

- Build and expose OGC collections as output.

Statistical Computation (Edwards & McKee, 1997):

1. Reference Period Fitting (1980–2010):

Total monthly precipitation data from the 30-year reference period is extracted from the ERA5-Land monthly means dataset. The distribution of monthly precipitation accumulations is fitted to a two-parameter gamma distribution using the L-moments method. The gamma distribution is chosen due to its suitability for modeling climatological precipitation series. Only non-zero precipitation values are considered in the fitting process.

2. Probability Adjustment:

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the fitted gamma distribution is adjusted to account for the probability of zero precipitation events, as follows:

$$Fp_0(x; \alpha, \lambda) = p_0 + (1 - p_0) \cdot F(x; \alpha, \lambda)$$

where p_0 is the frequency of zero-precipitation months in the reference period.

3. Transformation to Standard Normal Variable (SPI):

The adjusted cumulative probabilities are transformed into a standard normal variable (Z-score) with mean 0 and standard deviation 1, using the numerical method described by *Abramowitz and Stegun (1965)*. This transformed value is the SPI, which quantifies the anomaly relative to the historical norm.

Datasets: The calculation relies on two primary data sources:

1. ERA5 Monthly Means (1980–2010): used as the climatological reference for fitting the gamma distribution. These long-term statistics represent the baseline against which anomalies are measured.
2. ERA5 Hourly Data: used to aggregate precipitation over the 3-month windows for the period of interest. Data is extracted and processed on a monthly basis to ensure consistency and accuracy in the monitoring framework.

Outputs: The outputs of the SPI-3 calculation include:

1. An OGC Coverage Collection with a spatial resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$, containing grid-based SPI-3 values for the analysed period.
2. A GeoJSON vector collection containing zonal statistics computed over predefined hydrological basins within the region. These statistics include:
 - Minimum and Maximum
 - Percentiles: 5th, 10th, 30th, 50th (median), 70th, 90th, and 95th

Bias Correction of Seasonal Forecasts Temperature and Precipitation

Purpose: This process is designed to monitor seasonal forecasts of minimum/maximum temperature and precipitation over the next six months. Since raw forecast outputs often contain systematic biases due to model imperfections, a bias correction using a parametric quantile mapping approach is applied to improve their comparability with historical observations. The correction ensures that forecasted values are on the same statistical scale as the reference data, thereby increasing the reliability and usability of the forecasts for downstream applications.

Methodology: The system operates monthly, triggered by an automated cron-based process, and is implemented as part of a PyGeoAPI service. For each monthly run, the system:

- Retrieves seasonal forecast data initialized in the current month,
- Extracts daily values for the following six months (lead months 1–6),
- Applies a bias correction to each ensemble member's monthly precipitation, minimum temperature, and maximum temperature values.

Bias correction factor estimation:

For each grid cell, initialization month, and lead month:

- Forecast data (all ensemble members, all available years) are used to fit a statistical model:
 - Gamma distribution (loc = 0) for precipitation
 - Gaussian distribution for temperature
- Corresponding reference (observed) data for the same target month are used to fit a second model of the same type.

Bias correction application:

For each lead month:

- Forecast values are transformed into the normal space using the fitted distribution parameters (similar to the SPI computation, i.e., computing Z-scores).
- The observed distribution parameters for the corresponding target month are then used to transform the Z-scores back to the data space, producing bias-corrected values.

Datasets: The process utilizes data from the Copernicus dataset “*Seasonal forecast daily and subdaily data on single levels*”, which provides ensemble forecasts for multiple variables and lead times across the globe.

Outputs: The process generates six datasets for each monthly run: the raw forecast values of precipitation, minimum temperature, and maximum temperature, along with their respective bias-corrected versions. For the three corrected variables, the system produces and publishes three separate OGC Coverage Collections. Each collection contains 51 variables, corresponding to the 51 ensemble members of the forecast model, and provides spatially distributed monthly values ready for integration into geospatial platforms or climate monitoring services.

Front-End and Web GUI

The front-end platform developed for the Georgian Living Lab offers an integrated and interactive interface for accessing climate and hydrological information relevant to flood and drought risk management in the Alazani River basin. The web interface is structured to support both expert users and local stakeholders, and combines forecast data, historical trends, and interactive maps for a comprehensive user experience and is composed by the following main sections:

Hydro Forecasts (GLOFAS & SMHI Models)

- View river discharge forecasts for selected stations (e.g., Shakriani #440).
- Access ensemble forecast data with percentile ranges (e.g., 5–95%, 10–90%)
- Switch between GLOFAS and SMHI hydrological models.
- Choose different visualization modes: raw model outputs, percentile plots, box plots.
- Identify potential flood peaks and monitor trends in river discharge.

Temperature & Precipitation Forecasts

- Explore monthly forecasts for temperature (max/min) and total precipitation up to 6 months ahead.
- Visualized via box plots for both historical reference and future projections.

SPI Index (Standardized Precipitation Index)

- Access both historical and seasonal SPI data to assess drought conditions.
- Interactive maps showing SPI status across administrative regions for given months.
- Based on ERA5-Land reanalysis for historical data and Copernicus seasonal forecasts for projections.

The Web Front-End platform integrates multiple climate and hydrological datasets to provide actionable climate services for managing drought and flood risks and a common mapping interface to select area/station of interest.

Hydro Forecasts (River Discharge Prediction)

A central component of the interface is the Hydro Forecasts section (Figure 24, Figure 25), where users can explore river discharge projections for selected stations such as Shakriani (#440). The hydrographs display ensemble forecasts derived from both the GLOFAS and SMHI models, allowing users to switch between data sources. Forecast uncertainty is represented through percentile bands (e.g., 5–95%, 10–90%, 30–70%), helping users assess both typical and extreme discharge scenarios. Historical discharge data is also shown for comparison, and reference threshold lines (e.g., “Extreme High” or “Above Normal”) are included to support flood risk assessment. The system allows zooming into different time windows, from one month to the full year. Historically observed discharge data shown in the interface are automatically acquired via FTP and OTC bucket from local hydrological monitoring sources managed by the Georgian authorities and regularly integrated into the backend data storage.

The following figures illustrate the landing page of the service, which features a general dropdown menu on the left for selecting both the section and the monitoring station of interest. The central map (described later on) displays the station names and their locations, while the right-hand panel presents the initial visualization of the Hydro Forecasts section, typically showing the forecast ensemble. At the bottom of the interface, monthly daily discharge values are also displayed.

Historical daily observed discharge data have been provided as separate ASCII files to be embedded in the platform once. While for specific near real-time monitoring stations Shakriani #440 discharge and level data an FTP space is the source of the retrieved data.

Figure 24- screen shots from the hydro forecast component_main page and selectable stations.

Figure 25- screen shots from the hydro forecast component_ average monthly graph.

Detailed interface elements are listed hereafter:

Main Panel:

- Displays hydrographs of forecasted river discharge for specific monitoring stations (e.g. Shakriani #440).
- Time range: from February to December 2025, or user-defined zoom (1m, 3m, 6m, All).

Key functionalities:

- Ensemble Forecast Visualization: Displays uncertainty using percentiles:
 - 10–90%, 5–95%, 30–70%, 40–60%, and 50th percentile (median).
 - Useful to understand both the most likely discharge and possible extremes.
- Historical discharge line: A dashed black line shows real discharge data for comparison with forecast.
- Threshold lines:
 - Extreme High (red dashed)
 - Above Normal (blue dashed)

These are reference thresholds to assess flood risk.

Switchable Data Sources (Dropdown):

- GLOFAS (Global Flood Awareness System)
- SMHI (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute)

Visualization Modes (Ensemble Dropdown):

- Ensemble: Full ensemble spread
- 50th Percentile: Single line median forecast
- Models: Individual models
- BoxPlot / BoxPlot w/ P: Statistical summaries for each forecast period

Monthly Temperature & Precipitation Forecasts

In the Temperature and Precipitation Forecasts section (Figure 26, Figure 27) users can view monthly forecasts at the municipal or basin scale—such as for Kvareli Municipality. Forecasts extend up to six months ahead and are displayed using box plots that show the spread and median of projected values. Maximum and minimum temperatures are visualized separately, and the interface clearly reveals seasonal trends, such as cooling toward winter. Similarly, monthly precipitation forecasts are provided, highlighting dry or wet anomalies through boxplot visualizations. This component is particularly useful for agricultural planning, anticipating heatwaves or heavy rainfall, and managing drought preparedness.

Hydro Forecast

SPI Index Historical

SPI Index Forecast

Forecast Temp. & Precip.

ICISK home page

v1.0.54

Figure 26 - Temperature and Precipitation Forecasts list and map of selectable municipalities.

Monthly Forecast for Temperature and Precipitation at confluence point, Municipalità di Kvareli, Cachezia, Georgia

Figure 27 - Temperature and Precipitation Forecasts plots for the selected area.

Detailed interface elements are listed hereafter:

Overview Panel:

- Combines temperature and precipitation forecasts at municipality or basin level (example: Kvareli Municipality).
Top Chart – Temperature Forecast (°C):
- Tmax (red boxplots) and Tmin (blue boxplots) displayed monthly.
- Shows median and spread (interquartile range) over the forecast horizon (Jul–Dec 2025).
Clear seasonal cooling trend visible toward winter.

Bottom Chart – Precipitation Forecast (mm):

- Monthly total precipitation (tp acc) shown with boxplots.
- Median line overlaid.
- Indicates dry and wet anomalies month by month.

SPI Index – Historical & Forecasted Drought Monitoring

Another key module is the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) section (example in Figure 28), which supports drought monitoring using both historical and seasonal forecast data. Historical SPI maps, based on ERA5-Land reanalysis (1950–present), show precipitation anomalies across the basin, with a colour scale ranging from deep blue (wet conditions) to red (drought). Forecast SPI data, sourced from the Copernicus Climate Data Store, offers seasonal outlooks for regions such as Zemo Kedi and Dali, capturing expected transitions between wet and dry phases over time. These tools are instrumental for early warning, irrigation planning, and regional vulnerability assessments.

Figure 28- SPI index in forecast mode visualized through the service.

Detailed interface elements are listed hereafter:

SPI (Standardized Precipitation Index):

Measures **precipitation anomalies** relative to long-term climatology. Values:

- Near 0 = Normal
- < -1 = Moderate to severe drought
- 1 = Wet period

a) SPI Index – Historical View

- Data Source: ERA5-Land reanalysis (from 1950 to present)
- Map shows SPI values interpolated across the Alazani Basin for June 2025.
- Each region is color-coded from deep blue (wet) to red (dry).
- Labels indicate key locations (e.g., Artana, Lelovani, Patdo).

b) SPI Index – Forecast View

- Data Source: Copernicus Climate Data Store – Seasonal Forecast
- Forecast window: Jun–Nov 2025
- Interpolated forecast SPI maps show expected drought or wetness conditions.
- Regions like Zemo Kedi and Dali can be seen transitioning between conditions over time.

Interactive Map Interface

Finally, the interface includes a fully interactive map viewer, built using the ReactJS framework combined with OpenLayers and Highcharts libraries, similar to the technical stack adopted for the Italian Living Lab. This interactive viewer, based on OpenStreetMap, integrates multiple geographic layers, enabling comprehensive spatial analysis of climate-related risks. The available interactive layers include:

- Hydro stations
- Rivers
- Catchment basins
- SPI anomaly maps

Users can click directly on individual hydro stations to display detailed hydrographs, while the integrated layer toggle feature allows seamless switching between different datasets (such as SPI anomalies versus river discharge data). This dynamic visualization significantly enhances regional situational awareness and effectively supports stakeholder decision-making.

- Layer toggle enables focus on specific datasets (e.g. SPI vs river discharge).

Summary and outlook

The Georgia Climate Service platform has been designed with usability, flexibility, and accessibility for a broad range of stakeholders involved in climate risk management and water resource planning in mind.

Built on a modular architecture, the system combines a robust backend infrastructure with an intuitive and interactive front-end interface, allowing users to seamlessly access and interpret hydrological and climate information relevant to the Alazani River Basin.

The web interface is developed using a customised React-based template derived from the *React-free-react-admin* framework, integrated with open-source components specifically adapted to the needs of the Living Lab. Key visualisation modules include react-map, which embeds an OpenLayers map for interactive navigation of spatial datasets (such as shapefiles and raster layers), and ensemble-chart, a JavaScript component enabling the display of river discharge forecasts and climate indicators through dynamic graphs and statistical plots.

The graphical user interface (from Figure 24 to Figure 28) is structured around three main interactive zones: a left-hand sidebar, a central map viewer, and a right-hand panel dedicated to data visualisation. Through the sidebar, users can navigate between different monitoring stations or thematic sections (e.g., hydrological forecasts, temperature/precipitation outlooks, SPI index). The central map offers a geographic overview of Points/areas of Interest, including river basins, municipalities and hydrological stations, while the right-hand panel provides detailed outputs such as ensemble time series, percentile bands, box plots, and SPI maps. A date slider allows users to explore both near-term and seasonal forecasts up to six months ahead.

To enhance usability, the interface includes several accessibility features: it supports interaction via keyboard, is compatible with screen readers, and adapts responsively to smartphones and tablets. Users with no programming experience can interact with the system through intuitive dropdowns, sliders, and map-based controls. The default visualisation settings, contextual tooltips, and clear legends make it easy to interpret forecast uncertainty, historical trends, and drought indices without technical expertise.

Furthermore, the Georgia Climate Service Living Lab combines seasonal forecasts from SMHI with local observational data to support climate forecasting and risk assessment in the Alazani River Basin. The backend infrastructure includes bias correction, downscaling, and post-processing steps, managed through Docker-based services for streamlined data ingestion, storage, and computation.

On the front-end side, the platform—built using React, OpenLayers, and Highcharts—provides an intuitive and responsive interface that, as mentioned, enables users to interact with climate and hydrological information through maps, graphs, and sliders. The design prioritises ease of use, allowing users to explore forecasts, compare historical and projected data, and adjust.

4.7. Lesotho Living Lab (LL7)

Climate Data Integration and Back-end components

The main climate data exploited in the Lesotho CS are Seasonal Forecast products of Precipitation.

Seasonal forecasts are produced by several climate institutes. For Lesotho LL I-CISK Climate Service, we considered two specific products: the low-resolution SEAS5, produced by ECMWF and available in the Copernicus Climate Data Store with a resolution of 1x1 degree (approximately 100x100 km), and the SMHI seasonal forecast, which is based on a downscaled version of the high-resolution SEAS5 with a resolution of around 25 km, provided by SMHI via dedicated FTP server.

A preliminary model skill assessment for drought occurrence was conducted. The results indicate that there is no significant difference between the two forecast products for the specific use case. Detailed information about this skill assessment included in deliverable D3.4.

Ultimately, the pre - operational service integrates the ECMWF low-resolution SEAS5 data because it is publicly available and can ensure sustainability beyond the duration of the project.

In order to assess and map the potential number of populations under drought risk a density population layer has been integrated in the service.

The architecture of the Lesotho climate service platform is built on a cloud-based infrastructure, utilizing Docker containers. Key components include the frontend-service, backend-service, data ingestor, data storage.

The frontend is implemented as an Angular-based IBF dashboard, featuring interactive maps (using OpenLayers)

The backend-service is based on pygeoapi and serves data like series to the frontend. Climate models and algorithms are also executed from the backend-service like customized processes.

The data ingestor handles the retrieval and preprocessing of climate data, which are then stored in a S3-like data storage and/or a Database.

The back end of the Lesotho Climate Service application is designed to automate the assessment of drought risk by processing historical and seasonal precipitation forecast data. This involves a series of computational steps to analyse precipitation data, compute relevant statistics, and visualise the results. Below is a detailed description of the key functionalities implemented in the code.

Data Processing and Handling

Function: Data Ingestion and Preparation

Forecast Data: Seasonal forecast data period under investigation is loaded from NetCDF files or automatically ingested by Data Ingestor connected to Copernicus CDS. This data consists of 51 ensemble members, providing a range of possible future precipitation scenarios.

Identifying Drought Risk Areas Based on Below-Normal Precipitation Probability

A precipitation seasonal forecast helps final users to understand how much rain may occur over a whole season, instead of predicting exact amounts of rainfall for each day. This approach is more practical because daily weather can be very unpredictable, while seasonal patterns are more stable and easier to anticipate.

The implemented methodology aggregates monthly precipitation forecasts temporally over three months and provides them with at least three months lead time. For instance, exploiting the forecast issued in September, we compute the predicted rainfall accumulation for the upcoming December, January, and February.

To assess these patterns, we use tercile probabilities, which means we divide the range of possible seasonal rainfall into three equal parts: below average, average, and above average. To calculate the probability of below-average rainfall, we analyse historical hindcast data and compare it with the current seasonal forecast. For instance, if we see that there's a 40% chance of receiving rainfall amounts in the lowest third of the historical data range, we consider that area to be experiencing below-average rainfall.

The probability of below normal is computed counting the number of forecast ensembles with accumulated precipitation value at or below the lower tercile and then dividing by the number of ensemble members (51). We define a drought at a specific location when the probability of being in the lower tercile (the lowest third of rainfall amounts) exceeds 25%.

Ultimately, we calculate drought risk and the exposed population at the district level in Lesotho, as preparedness plans are typically coordinated at this scale. For each district, to estimate the exposed population, we sum the number of people living in areas within the district where the probability of below-normal precipitation exceeds the defined threshold. A district is classified as being at risk of drought if at least 10% of its area falls within this high-probability zone.

Front-End and Web GUI

In collaboration with National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies and other partners, the Netherlands Red Cross 510 has developed the Impact-Based Forecasting Portal (IBF Portal). This digital one-stop-shop provides crucial information to support disaster managers in making informed decisions during Anticipatory Action operations. The IBF Portal presents timely data on the potential impacts of incoming disasters, enabling decision-makers to implement pre-agreed early actions effectively. The portal was designed based on insights from over 160 co-design sessions with disaster managers, Red Cross Red Crescent Movement personnel, governmental and civil society stakeholders, and input from knowledge institutions and other humanitarian organisations.

The I-CISK Lesotho CS is integrated in the Front-End of the IBF Portal. This helps ensure sustainability, making it easier for the Netherlands Red Cross to maintain the platform and continue supporting stakeholders in the country beyond the project's duration.

Figure 29 – Impact-Based Forecasting Portal

A description of the main Front-End components is reported here below.

The portal interface is organized into three main sections:

Left panel: Displays general information, including the current date and time of the latest model run, a greeting with the user's name, and quick-access buttons for the alert log, IBF guide, trigger explanation, and export view. A note indicates whether any alerts were issued in the past.

Top bar: Shows the portal title and the logged-in username, with an option to log out or manage the account.

Main section - Forecast and Map: At the top, a timeline displays a calendar starting from the current date and extending one year into the future. Just below, a summary panel shows whether a drought is predicted, along with figures for exposed and total population.

The map displays Lesotho's districts, with optional data layers accessible via a dropdown menu in the bottom right. These layers include Red Cross branch locations, population, exposed population, and below-normal rainfall probability. A legend indicates any areas where a drought has been triggered.

The portal can be in one of three states, depending on the forecast results:

1. **No-Trigger State:** No drought risk is detected anywhere in the country. In this state, no warnings or alerts are shown. The left panel displays general information only, and the map remains unshaded. Users are informed that no action is currently required.
2. **Warning State** (see Figure 29: Drought risk is identified based on forecast data and thresholds).
 - In the left panel, a warning box appears, summarizing the expected timing of the drought, the forecast source, and listing the districts at risk along with the estimated exposed population per district.
 - The forecast summary at the top updates to reflect the number of exposed districts and population.
 - On the map, affected districts are shaded in varying tones of purple, indicating the number of people exposed in each.
 - On the timeline, the relevant rainy season period is highlighted, showing when the warning applies.
3. **Trigger State** (see Figure 29): This state is activated when the drought risk has been officially confirmed. It indicates that anticipatory actions should be implemented. The trigger is set manually by authorised users, currently limited to the Anticipatory Action Coordinator of the Lesotho Red Cross Society. These users confirm the presence of drought risk based on information received from the Lesotho Meteorological Service at the start of the rainy season. To set the trigger, the users click the "Set trigger" button in the left panel and select the specific districts expected to be affected. Once the trigger is set
 - The top banner turns purple with a warning icon
 - A red-bordered box in the left panel confirms the trigger, showing the expected month of impact, the name of the user who activated it and the date it was set and the list of triggered districts, with population exposure figures.
 - The map now shows these triggered districts outlined in red. Their fill colour still reflects population exposure, as per the map legend.
 - The timeline at the top highlights the relevant month with a purple triangle icon, consistent with earlier warning stages.

- Notifications are automatically sent out via email and WhatsApp to all users, ensuring timely awareness and action.
- This state is the operational signal for starting early action plans and mobilising resources.

Summary and outlook

The Lesotho Climate Service Living Lab uses seasonal forecast products to assess drought risk across Lesotho. Forecasts are sourced from ECMWF's SEAS5 system, offering precipitation outlooks up to six months ahead. These forecasts undergo bias adjustment and aggregation at the district level.

The platform runs on a cloud-based backend using Docker and NestJS, which handles data ingestion, storage, and API services for the Impact-Based Forecasting (IBF) system.

The frontend is implemented as an Angular-based IBF dashboard, featuring interactive maps (using OpenLayers) and visualizations for exploring hazard and population exposure data.

Users interact with the portal to assess drought risk via maps that display areas with elevated probabilities of below-normal precipitation, overlaid with population data. This enables clear identification of districts and populations most at risk. Embedded within the Netherlands Red Cross's IBF Portal, the system supports anticipatory action, disaster preparedness, and resource planning.

5. Report Quality Goals and testing.

Note: The quality goals and testing regimes have not changed since D5.2 and are repeated for ease of readability.

Key quality goals

The I-CISK Climate Service platform is designed with several key quality goals in mind to ensure it meets the needs of stakeholders effectively. These goals are centred around usability, accuracy, reliability, performance, and scalability:

Usability:

Intuitive Interface: Ensure the platform is easy to navigate for users with varying levels of technical expertise.

Accessibility: Provide features that make the platform accessible to users with limited programming skills, including comprehensive documentation and guided workflows.

Localization: Support multiple languages to cater to a diverse user base.

Accuracy:

Data Integrity: Maintain high standards of data integrity by implementing robust data validation and correction mechanisms.

Model Precision: Use advanced statistical methods and bias-adjustment techniques to ensure the accuracy of climate forecasts and predictions.

Reliability:

Consistency: Ensure consistent performance and availability of the platform through rigorous testing and monitoring.

Fault Tolerance: Implement mechanisms to handle and recover from errors gracefully without affecting user experience.

Performance:

Efficiency: Optimise data processing and computation to deliver results quickly.

Scalability: Design the system to handle increasing amounts of data and user requests efficiently.

Elasticity: Ensure the platform can scale dynamically to accommodate varying loads and user demands.

Futureproofing: Architect the system to be flexible and adaptable to incorporate new data sources, models, and features over time.

Results from Initial Testing Phases and User Feedback

Initial Testing Phases:

The I-CISK Climate Service platform underwent several initial testing phases to ensure it meets the set quality goals. These phases included functionality testing, performance testing, and usability testing.

Functionality Testing:

Scope: Verified all features and functionalities of the platform, including data ingestion, processing, visualisation, and user interactions.

Outcome: Identified and resolved issues related to data integration, algorithm implementation, and user interface glitches. Ensured that all modules work seamlessly together.

Performance Testing:

Scope: Evaluated the system's performance under different loads and usage scenarios.

Outcome: Optimised data processing workflows and improved the efficiency of computational tasks. Enhanced the responsiveness of the user interface, even with large datasets.

Usability Testing:

Scope: Assessed the platform's usability by involving users with varying levels of technical expertise.

Outcome: Gathered valuable feedback on the ease of use, intuitiveness, and overall user experience. Implemented changes to improve navigation, simplify complex workflows, and enhance visual clarity.

User Feedback:

User feedback played a crucial role in refining the I-CISK Climate Service platform. Here are some key insights and actions taken based on user feedback:

Interface Design:

Feedback: Users appreciated the clean and intuitive design but suggested improvements in navigation and data visualisation options.

Action: Enhanced the navigation structure, added more interactive elements, and provided customizable visualisation tools.

Data Accessibility:

Feedback: Users requested easier access to historical and forecast data, along with more detailed information on data sources and processing methods.

Action: Improved data access features provided detailed metadata for datasets and included comprehensive documentation and tooltips within the platform.

Performance and Speed:

Feedback: Some users experienced slow performance when handling large datasets or running complex queries.

Action: Optimised backend processing, implemented efficient data storage solutions, and enhanced the performance of critical algorithms.

Support and Training:

Feedback: Users highlighted the need for better support and training materials to help them make the most of the platform's features.

Action: Developed a series of tutorial videos, comprehensive user guides, and an integrated help system. Also, organised training sessions and webinars.

Conclusion

The initial testing phases and user feedback have been instrumental in shaping the I-CISK Climate Service platform. By focusing on usability, accuracy, reliability, performance, and scalability, the platform is well-equipped to meet the diverse needs of its stakeholders. Ongoing feedback and continuous improvement will ensure that the platform remains a valuable tool for climate data analysis and decision-making.

6. Challenges and Solutions

The implementation of the I-CISK platform across diverse Living Labs has provided valuable lessons on the complexities of co-designing climate services. Throughout the development phases, several recurring practical and technical challenges emerged, together with effective solutions adopted by the consortium to ensure successful outcomes.

- **CHALLENGE:** Discussion with LL hosts and stakeholders are very valuable but need time. This amount of time has been underestimated in the project design.
SOLUTION: Implementation of CSTF boosting productivity. (Later) adapt the focus based on needs of the LL to provide most valuable and exploitable, which might slightly deviate from what has been envisioned in the proposal phase.
- **CHALLENGE:** Availability of external data sources was in the past month of varying quality (access and data quality wise)
SOLUTION: incorporate data quality checks and (temporarily) store data in the own infrastructure opposed to purely access it through public APIs
- **CHALLENGE:** delay of provision of (local) data
SOLUTION: using synthetic data, but this requires additional work when (i) discussing results with users explaining the source/nature of the data and (ii) replacing the synthetic data with real data when it becomes available
- **CHALLENGE:** Keeping track of details and mid/ long-term decisions and discussions with many people in different constellations
SOLUTION: We found that a shared online office document (in our case google slides) was a good medium for keeping track of the current state as well as a place for discussions because it allows for text and images to be shared along with a commentary function.
- **CHALLENGE:** While the project and resources come to an end, each LL still has several new ideas and sees refinement opportunities. While this underpins the engagement in the co-design, it also poses a challenge.
SOLUTION: Over the period starting PM 37, this limitation has been made clear by WP5 and the CSTF have jointly prioritised features and refinements of the CS. Further ideas and requests are kept in a back-log of the respective repositories and could directly be addressed in desired further development.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

The I-CISK project has successfully developed and deployed a robust, scalable, and modular climate service platform designed to deliver actionable climate insights to diverse stakeholders across multiple regions and Living Labs. Central to these achievements has been the seamless integration of diverse climate datasets, spanning global sources such as Copernicus ERA5 and GLOFAS, regional forecasts provided by SMHI, and detailed local monitoring data collected from regional authorities and institutions. Leveraging a cloud-based architecture hosted on the Open Telekom Cloud, the technical infrastructure employs advanced containerization and orchestration tools (Docker and Kubernetes) that guarantee efficient data processing, flexibility, and reliable performance at scale.

A core innovation within the I-CISK platform is its modular back-end framework. At the heart of this framework lies the Climate Data Ingestor Docker, a component responsible for automated data retrieval, preprocessing, and standardization. Coupled with a centralised S3-compatible storage solution and the Pygeoapi backend service, this modular architecture not only ensures efficient data handling and compliance with open geospatial standards but also significantly enhances the reusability and scalability of the components beyond the scope of the current project.

To facilitate broader adoption and reuse, several modular components have been identified as particularly suited for transfer and further exploitation in future initiatives. The table below summarises these common components, their core functionalities, and their potential applications beyond the I-CISK Living Labs:

Table 3 Common components, their core functionalities, and potential applications beyond the Living Labs

Common Component	Description and Functionality	Reuse and Transfer Potential	Common Component
Climate Data Ingestor Docker	Automated retrieval and preprocessing of climate datasets (FTP, APIs), standardizing diverse sources into consistent data streams.	Easily adaptable to integrate new data providers and regional climate datasets.	Climate Data Ingestor Docker
Centralised Cloud Storage (S3-compatible)	Optimized storage solution designed specifically for efficient handling of large climate datasets.	Applicable as a reliable backend for future climate service implementations and other geospatial data platforms.	Centralised Cloud Storage (S3-compatible)
Pygeoapi Backend Service	Standardized, open-source backend providing OGC-compliant APIs for data access and processing.	Scalable and extendable backend suitable for diverse climate and environmental data services.	Pygeoapi Backend Service

Alongside these robust technical developments, considerable emphasis has been placed on stakeholder-driven front-end solutions. Through iterative co-design processes, the project developed intuitive graphical

user interfaces that cater effectively to the needs of users with varying technical expertise. Interactive visualisation capabilities provided by libraries such as ReactJS, OpenLayers, Highcharts, Leaflet, and Plotly have significantly improved the accessibility, usability, and interpretability of complex climate forecasts and data. Comprehensive testing, multilingual support, and thorough documentation have further enhanced the platform's accessibility and user-friendliness.

Each Living Lab benefited from tailored deployments of the common technological framework, adapted to address specific local contexts and user requirements. These customizations showcase the modularity and flexibility of the platform, confirming its readiness for future regional and thematic scalability.

The I-CISK Climate Service Platform, built upon a foundation of open-source components and cloud-based architecture, is inherently designed for sustainability and scalability, facilitating its future application and integration within the broader European data infrastructure landscape.

The platform's commitment to open-source solutions, such as pygeoapi for the Climate Data Ingestor Docker and frameworks like React, OpenLayers, and OpenPioneer for the front-end, ensures long-term viability and reduces reliance on proprietary systems. This approach fosters a collaborative development environment, allowing for continuous improvements and adaptations by a wider community. Furthermore, the use of Docker and Kubernetes for containerization and orchestration promotes maintainability and simplifies updates, ensuring the platform remains robust and functional over time. The focus on tailored solutions for each Living Lab, while leveraging common components, also contributes to sustainability by addressing specific regional needs and increasing the likelihood of local adoption and continued use beyond the project's lifetime.

The cloud-based infrastructure, hosted on the Open Telekom Cloud (OTC) and utilizing Docker and Kubernetes technologies, provides significant scalability. This allows the platform to handle increasing volumes of climate data and accommodate a growing number of Living Labs without compromising performance. The modular architecture, where each component has its own workload and service enables independent scaling of individual parts of the system. The Climate Data Ingestor Docker, with its ability to ingest data from multiple sources and process it into cloud-optimized formats, is designed to scale with the expanding availability of climate data. The integration of bias correction and downscaling processes as OGC API Processes further enhances scalability by allowing these computationally intensive tasks to be integrated into custom workflows and executed efficiently.

The selection of OTC as the cloud computing environment is strategic, as it is a contributor to the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, serving as a main dissemination endpoint for Copernicus data. This eases the integration of the I-CISK platform with existing European data infrastructures. The Climate Data Ingestor Docker, being OGC compliant and based on pygeoapi, ensures interoperability and ease of data exchange with other systems adhering to open geospatial standards. The platform's ability to ingest data from sources like Copernicus and ECMWF, and to provide data via OGC APIs, positions it as a valuable component within the European data ecosystem. The development of widely applicable downscaling and bias-correcting processes, compatible across Europe and for different variables, further supports the re-use and longevity of the CS platform, enabling its transfer to other geographic areas or application contexts and strengthening its contribution to European climate service initiatives.

Looking forward, the strategic focus of I-CISK now shifts towards sustainability, long-term impact, and exploitation. Given that further technical development resources are limited as the project concludes, upcoming efforts will concentrate on securing sustainable funding mechanisms, developing strategic partnerships, and promoting capacity-building initiatives to empower the Living Labs, as well other communities and local authorities in their use of climate data for informed, proactive decision-making.

Additionally, integration with established infrastructures such as the Copernicus Data Space Environment (CDSE) is actively being explored, ensuring the long-term availability, dissemination, and continuity of I-CISK's developed climate services.

Detailed exploitation strategies and pathways towards sustainability have been elaborated in separate WP5 deliverables (D 5.5 Business model storylines for sustainable CS exploitation), providing concrete guidance for ensuring the lasting adoption, expansion, and impact of the innovations achieved through the I-CISK project.

8. Appendices

Acronyms

API – Application Programming Interface
CDD – Cooling Degree Days
CDS – Climate Data Store
CDSE – Copernicus Data Space Environment
CIS – Climate Information Services
CNN – Convolutional Neural Network
CSTF – Climate Service Task Forces
DBS – Distribution-Based Scaling
DJF – December, January, February
ENS – Ensemble
ERA5 – ECMWF Reanalysis version 5
ESGF – Earth System Grid Federation
FTP – File Transfer Protocol
GEOSS – Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GLOFAS – Global Flood Awareness System
GUI – Graphical User Interface
IBF – Impact-Based Forecasting
I-CISK – Innovative Climate Information Services for Knowledge
IDW – Inverse Distance Weighting
JSON – JavaScript Object Notation
LL – Living Lab
MAE – Mean Absolute Error
MidAS – Multi-scale bias AdjuStment
NetCDF – Network Common Data Form
OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium
OTC – Open Telekom Cloud
POI – Point of Interest
RMSE – Root Mean Squared Error
S3 – Simple Storage Service
SMHI – Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
SPI – Standard Precipitation Index
SPI-3 – Standardized Precipitation Index (3-month interval)
STAC – SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TCI – Tourism Climatic Index
UHI – Urban Heat Island
WP – Work Package
ZARR – Format for chunked, compressed, N-dimensional arrays

I-CISK

HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

Colophon:

This report has been prepared by the H2020 Research Project “Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge (I-CISK)”. This research project is a part of the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme call, “Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal (H2020-LC-GD-2020)”, and has been developed in response to the call topic “Developing end-user products and services for all stakeholders and citizens supporting climate adaptation and mitigation (LC-GD-9-2-2020)”. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037293.

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